

Synthesis of Findings on the Impact of Institutional Frameworks from the Set of 15 Case Studies

MATS Deliverable 4.1

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Summary

This report looks at the impact of institutional frameworks (domestic laws, European Union legislation, and international agreements) in the 15 case studies (CS) and aims at synthesizing the related learnings therefrom.

The CS reports show variety in terms of completeness and detail of analysis on legal and institutional matters, also reflect the ongoing CS work and the differences in CS focus concerning analysis methods and empirical settings. To a variable degree, CS reports focus on international trade, domestic law, supply chain organization, competition, food production, investment and social and environmental sustainability questions. In other words, the CS reports vary in terms of in-depth consideration of legal, governance and institutional aspects.

Furthermore, several areas of law, such as international environmental law and human rights law, have received especially little CS coverage. Also, other areas of law related to intellectual property (IP) are receiving little attention, particularly concerning patents, trademarks, copyrights, and geographical indications. This is remarkable since such areas of law are related to competition and innovation issues and may be especially relevant in the future agricultural trade and sustainability nexus, considering also the forthcoming transition pathways analysis (WP5).

The report provides a synthesis of general findings and, based on current information, a dedicated focus for every CS.

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Introduction

The Making Agricultural Trade Sustainable (MATS) Horizon project has conducted comprehensive case studies across 15 diverse regions and agricultural sectors, each focusing on the institutional and legal frameworks governing sustainable agricultural trade. These case studies examine domestic, European, and international legal instruments that impact agricultural practices, trade dynamics, and sustainability goals. The overarching aim is to assess how these frameworks contribute to sustainable agricultural practices and trade, particularly in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) context.

Impact of Legal and Institutional Frameworks on Trade with the EU

The legal and institutional frameworks examined across the case studies play a pivotal role in shaping the trade relationships between the European Union and the countries analyzed. Compliance with EU regulations and international agreements is not merely a requirement for market access but also a critical factor in enhancing the competitiveness of agricultural exports. For example, adherence to the EU's stringent food safety and sustainability standards, such as the General Food Law and voluntary sustainability certifications, enables producers in countries like Tanzania, Ghana, and Finland to secure and expand their market presence within the EU.

Moreover, these frameworks impact trade by facilitating smoother transactions and reducing trade barriers. The alignment of domestic laws with international agreements, such as the World Trade Organization's (WTO) Sanitary and Phytosanitary (SPS) Agreement and Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT) Agreement, ensures that agricultural products meet the required health, safety, and quality standards, thus preventing trade disruptions. Additionally, preferential trade agreements like the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) and the Everything But Arms (EBA) initiative provide developing countries with enhanced access to the EU market, promoting economic growth and development.

However, the case studies also reveal challenges in meeting the diverse and stringent requirements imposed by the EU. For many small-scale producers, particularly in developing countries, the cost and complexity of complying with these regulations can be prohibitive, leading to unequal access to trade opportunities. The case studies underscore the need for continuous capacity building, technological investment, and international cooperation to help these producers meet the required standards and fully benefit from the trade opportunities with the EU.

Structure of the Case Study Reports

Each case study report follows a consistent structure, allowing for a systematic analysis of the legal and institutional frameworks. The reports begin with an introduction that sets the context for the agricultural sector under review, identifying the essential commodities, stakeholders, and trade dynamics involved. This is followed by an examination of the relevant Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and how they align with the agricultural practices and policies in the region.

The legal instruments section forms the core of each report, detailing the domestic, European, and international laws that impact agricultural trade and sustainability. This includes an analysis of specific regulations, such as those governing food safety, environmental protection, labour rights, and market access. The reports also assess the effectiveness of these legal frameworks in promoting sustainable trade and identify any gaps or challenges that need to be addressed.

In addition, the reports examine the impact of these legal instruments on trade dynamics, particularly concerning the European Union. This includes discussions on market access, competitiveness, and the role of preferential trade agreements, such as the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) and the Everything But Arms (EBA) initiative. The reports conclude with an analysis of unaddressed areas of law and policy recommendations to enhance the sustainability and resilience of the agricultural sectors under study.

Place of the Current Summary

This summary provides valuable insights into the complex interplay between legal frameworks and sustainable agricultural trade. The document highlights the challenges and opportunities in aligning agricultural practices with global sustainability goals by analyzing diverse case studies from regions such as Sub-Saharan Africa, Scandinavia, and West Africa. The findings can help policymakers, international organizations, and stakeholders in the agricultural sector who are working to promote sustainable trade and improve the livelihoods of smallholder farmers globally.

This summary hopes to serve as a comprehensive resource on the institutional and legal frameworks that underpin sustainable agricultural trade. It offers a detailed analysis of how different regions and sectors navigate the challenges of compliance with international standards, integrating sustainability into agricultural practices, and enhancing market access in global trade. In addressing the strengths and weaknesses of existing frameworks, the document provides a roadmap for achieving more sustainable and equitable agricultural trade.

Case Study #1

Ability to reduce poverty of smallholder farmers through trade and value chains for coffee in Uganda and Tanzania

Lead organisation & name of lead contact: University of Helsinki; John Sumelius

Introduction

The Case Study offers a wide canvas on which different types of regulatory instruments are used to guide the activities examined. In the summary below, we attempt to carve out some of the domestic, European and international instruments deemed critical for assessing the sustainability of the activities and their impact on trade.

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

- **SDG 1. No Poverty:** Promoting sustainable agriculture is crucial for poverty reduction in rural areas of Uganda and Tanzania. Improved agricultural practices and market access can significantly enhance incomes for smallholder farmers. Increased trade opportunities, facilitated by compliance with international standards, help farmers achieve better prices for their products in the EU market, contributing to poverty alleviation. The report mentions efforts to increase the income of smallholder farmers through improved agricultural practices and market access. Farmers can secure better prices by improving coffee production and quality, thus reducing poverty levels in rural areas.
- **SDG 2. Zero Hunger:** Emphasising food security through sustainable agriculture helps local communities access sufficient, safe, and nutritious food. Improved coffee yields and diversified farming can reduce hunger and malnutrition. Higher quality and greater quantity of agricultural products, including coffee, enhance trade with the EU, providing economic benefits and contributing to national food security goals. Sustainable agricultural practices and diversification are emphasised to ensure food security. Enhanced agricultural productivity contributes to local food security and economic stability, reducing hunger.

- **SDG 8. Decent Work and Economic Growth:** Policies supporting fair labour practices, such as those outlined in the Employment and Labour Relations Regulations, ensure decent work conditions in the agricultural sector. This is crucial for sustaining economic growth and improving livelihoods. Adhering to labour standards boosts the reputation of Ugandan and Tanzanian coffee in the EU market, where consumers and businesses increasingly value ethical sourcing. Fair labour practices, safety standards, and wage regulations are highlighted. Ensuring decent work conditions attracts investment and enhances productivity, leading to economic growth.
- **SDG 12. Responsible Consumption and Production:** Encouraging sustainable production practices, such as those required by voluntary sustainability standards, ensures that agricultural activities do not harm the environment and that resources are used efficiently. Products certified under sustainability standards are more attractive in the EU market, with a growing demand for responsibly sourced goods. Adopting sustainability standards like Fair Trade and Organic ensures responsible production. Responsible production practices reduce environmental impact and enhance product appeal in international markets.
- **SDG 13. Climate Action:** Implementing climate-resilient agricultural practices helps mitigate climate change's effects, ensuring coffee farming's long-term viability. Initiatives aligned with the UNFCCC and Kyoto Protocol emphasise this goal. Compliance with climate action commitments enhances the sustainability profile of Ugandan and Tanzanian coffee, making it more appealing to environmentally conscious EU consumers and businesses. It emphasises climate-resilient farming practices and adherence to international climate agreements. Practices that mitigate climate change impacts ensure the long-term sustainability of agriculture and its resilience to climate-related disruptions.
- **SDG 15. Life on Land:** Protecting biodiversity and promoting sustainable land use are key components of this goal. Practices that prevent land degradation and promote soil health are essential for sustainable agriculture. Products grown with an emphasis on biodiversity and sustainable land management meet the rising EU demand for environmentally friendly products, enhancing market access and trade volumes. Sustainable land management and biodiversity conservation practices are promoted. Sustainable practices protect ecosystems, ensuring agricultural productivity and environmental health.
- **SDG 17: Partnerships for the Goals:** Collaboration with international organisations, NGOs, and private sector partners helps implement sustainable agricultural practices and improve market access. Effective partnerships are crucial

for resource mobilisation and knowledge sharing. Strong partnerships facilitate compliance with international trade standards and certifications, enhancing the ability of Uganda and Tanzania to compete in the EU market. Collaboration with international bodies, NGOs, and private sectors also improves agricultural practices and market access. Partnerships enhance resource mobilisation and technical support, facilitating compliance with international standards and improving market competitiveness.

Legal Instruments

1. Domestic Legislation in Uganda and Tanzania

Uganda and Tanzania have enacted specific laws to regulate and promote their coffee industries, which are critical for local economic development and international trade.

Uganda

- *National Coffee Policy 2013 and Uganda National Coffee Act 2021*

These laws provide a framework for developing, regulating, and promoting the coffee sector, including quality control and marketing. They aim to improve the competitiveness and sustainability of Ugandan coffee in the global market. These laws regulate and promote the coffee sector, focusing on quality control, licensing, and marketing. They aim to improve coffee production, processing, and trade. By establishing clear regulatory frameworks, these laws enhance the competitiveness and sustainability of Ugandan coffee, aligning with national economic goals and international market standards.

- *National Agricultural Research Act 2005*

The Act supports research and innovation in agriculture, essential for improving coffee yield and quality. It promotes advancements in coffee cultivation techniques, improving yield and quality, crucial for maintaining a competitive edge in the global market.

Tanzania

- *Coffee Industry Act No. 23 of 2001 and Coffee Industry Regulations 2013*

These regulations establish the Tanzania Coffee Board, which oversees the coffee industry's regulation, improvement, and development. They set quality control and

trade practices standards, ensuring the industry's alignment with domestic and international standards. These laws establish the Tanzania Coffee Board, set standards for quality control, and outline rules for coffee growing, processing, and marketing. These regulations ensure the orderly development of the coffee sector, enhancing production standards and marketability and supporting Tanzania's economic development goals.

- *Environmental Management Act 2004*

The Act mandates Environmental Impact Assessments (EIA) for projects with significant environmental impacts, ensuring that coffee production meets environmental sustainability standards. Also, Environmental Impact Assessments (EIA) are mandatory for projects likely to have significant environmental impacts. The Act ensures that coffee production adheres to environmental sustainability standards, supporting SDG 13 (Climate Action) and SDG 15 (Life on Land).

- *Employment and Labour Relations (General) Regulations 2017*

These regulations protect workers' rights, including fair wages, safe working conditions, and the right to form unions, which are crucial for maintaining a productive and motivated workforce in the agricultural sector. The Act covers workers' rights to form unions, bargain collectively, and conduct strikes. It aims to protect workers' rights, ensure fair wages, and ensure safe working conditions, which are crucial for a motivated workforce and sustainable industry growth.

2. International Legal Instruments

The case study references several international agreements and frameworks that significantly impact Uganda and Tanzania's agricultural and trade activities. These include:

- *UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and Kyoto Protocol*

These frameworks emphasise climate change mitigation and adaptation, influencing sustainable farming practices in both countries. The adherence to these protocols supports implementing climate-resilient agricultural methods, thus aligning local practices with global climate action goals. The case study emphasises general adherence to climate change mitigation and adaptation efforts. The Kyoto Protocol's mechanisms, such as emissions trading and the Clean Development Mechanism (CDM), are indirectly referenced by promoting sustainable agricultural practices to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. These provisions encourage adopting climate-friendly farming practices in Uganda and Tanzania, aiding in cultivating crops resilient

to climate change. This aligns with the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 13 on Climate Action.

- *Convention on Biological Diversity*

This Convention's focus on biodiversity conservation directly affects agricultural practices by promoting sustainable land management and the protection of ecosystems. The case study highlights measures for biodiversity conservation, such as sustainable land management practices that help maintain soil health and biodiversity. By promoting agricultural practices that protect biodiversity, the Convention supports SDG 15 (Life on Land), ensuring sustainable land use and the preservation of ecosystems.

- *United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification*

The Convention underscores efforts to combat land degradation, crucial for maintaining soil health and ensuring long-term agricultural productivity. Efforts to combat land degradation are a key focus, specifically mentioning sustainable farming practices that prevent soil erosion and maintain land productivity. These provisions are crucial for sustainable agriculture, directly impacting food security (SDG 2) and poverty reduction (SDG 1) by ensuring that the land remains fertile and productive.

- *WTO Agreements*

The Agreement on Sanitary and Phytosanitary Measures (SPS), Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT), and Trade Facilitation Agreement play vital roles in ensuring that agricultural exports meet international standards, thus facilitating smoother trade flows and market access.

- *SPS Agreement*: Ensures that coffee exports meet international health and safety standards, preventing the spread of pests and diseases.
- *TBT Agreement*: Addresses technical regulations and standards, ensuring that coffee products comply with international quality norms.
- *Trade Facilitation Agreement*: Aims to expedite the movement, release, and clearance of goods, simplifying trade procedures. These agreements facilitate smoother trade flows, enhance market access, and improve the competitiveness of Ugandan and Tanzanian coffee in the global market.

- *African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA)*

AfCFTA aims to reduce tariffs on goods, including coffee, enhance intra-African trade, and support economic growth. It also includes provisions on intellectual property rights and competition policy, which can impact the agricultural sector by promoting innovation and fair competition. The case study references tariff reductions on 90% of goods, economic growth through increased intra-African trade, and support for smallholder farmers. AfCFTA's provisions enhance trade opportunities for Uganda and Tanzania, promoting economic integration and boosting the coffee trade within Africa.

3. European Union Legislation

The case study references EU legislation and how it impacts production and trade.

- *EU General Food Law (Regulation EC No 178/2002)*

Establishes principles and requirements of food law and procedures in food safety, impacting how agricultural products are produced, processed, and traded.

- *Regulation EC No 852/2004 on the hygiene of foodstuffs*

It implements requirements based on the Hazard Analysis Critical Control Point (HACCP) methodology.

- *Regulation EC No 396/2005 on maximum residue levels of pesticides –*

The Regulation governs the maximum residue levels (MRLs) of pesticides in or on food and feed of plant and animal origin. Compliance with these regulations ensures that coffee exports meet EU safety and quality standards, facilitating market access and enhancing trade relationships.

During the survey, key informant interviews have established that the Tanzania Coffee Board (TCB) is aware of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005 and that proper mechanisms are in place to ensure that farmers are oriented on the adverse effects of using pesticides like clothianidin and thiamethoxam. It was further revealed that some smallholder farmers are now resorting to alternative agronomic practices that do not involve chemicals so that coffee produced in Tanzania always meets EU standards. Farmers are progressively being oriented to organic farming approaches, such as using natural fertilisers and composite manure that contribute to higher productivity levels through improvement in soil fertility. This awareness and the fact

that there is high demand for organic green coffee shall make farmers in the future benefit from the coffee value chain.

- *Commission Regulation (EC) 1881/2006 on Ochratoxin A (OTA)*

Ochratoxin A (OTA) mycotoxin is a common challenge in coffee beans and is often a reason for most border rejection of coffee consignments. The Commission Regulation (EC) 1881/2006 on setting maximum levels for specific contaminants in foodstuffs, including coffee. Based on this Regulation, the following limits apply to green coffee beans. Most of OTA is eliminated by as much as 85% during the roasting process. Thus, the Regulation applied more to roasted and soluble coffee to ensure the roasting process was done correctly.

Despite no limits for green beans, OTA contamination can occur during the post-harvest stages, which include processing, storage, and transport. Thus, managing moisture content throughout the entire processing and supply chain is important. During this study, coffee quality and testing officers at coffee processing factories such as KPL (Tchibo) and Macharere ported that they fully understand the Commission Regulation (EC) 1881/2006 requirements on OTA because their primary coffee market is the EU. Therefore, they try to observe these mycotoxin specifications by keeping their coffees at the recommended moisture content through sun drying and electricity dryers.

- *Commission Regulation (EC) 1881/2006 on Heavy metals*

Commission Regulation (EC) 1881/2006 also provides some prescriptions about limits on heavy metal contaminants. The commission has set some maximum levels for specific heavy metal contaminants in foodstuffs. The levels are measured in milligrams per kilogram of weight (mg/kg) or parts per million (ppm). However, based on this Regulation, there are no limits set specifically for coffee, although the EU Food law generally mandates that all food products enter the EU.

- *Regulation (EC) 1881/2006 on Mineral Oil Hydrocarbons (MOHs)*

Mineral Oil Hydrocarbons are chemicals, such as polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), that can contaminate food products during processing. Although no limits are established for coffee products on MOHs, their contamination can occur through often-used materials such as jute bags, fabricated using "batching oil" to soften the jute fibres before spinning. This compels exporters to use only jute bags that conform to the International Jute Organization Standards. During the survey, it was revealed that large-scale coffee exporters like Machare and cooperative societies like Ushiri,

Mamsera and Mruwia are aware of this requirement and that one or more times, they imported and used sacks imported from India, which contaminated their coffee. Having learned that these exporters have been compelled to look for alternative sources of better packaging materials, though at a higher cost to meet the EU market's requirements.

- *Plant Health*

Plant-based food products can introduce pests, weeds or diseases that could harm the importing country's humans, plants, or animals. Phytosanitary requirements can assist in preventing the introduction and spread of such harmful organisms. On 14 December 2019, the new EU put Plant Health Rules into force to improve the protection of the EU territory and its plants.

According to EU Regulation (EU) 2016/2031, all plants (including living parts of plants) entering the EU must be accompanied by a phytosanitary certificate that certifies the consignment complies with the law's requirements unless the product is listed in Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2018/2019 as exempt from this general requirement. Coffee is not one of the exempted crops for this purpose. In the originating country, harmful organisms can be minimised through appropriate planting material, good crop husbandry and sanitation practices, appropriate use of approved pesticides, and proper storage and transport practices. An authorised official in the country of origin must issue a phytosanitary certificate, which guarantees that the consignments are free from pests, weeds and diseases and meet the EU market's phytosanitary requirements.

Tanzania Plant Health and Pesticides Authorities (TPHPA) are mandated to issue the country's phytosanitary certificates. If a phytosanitary certificate does not accompany a consignment, or if pests, weeds or diseases are detected during an inspection at the importing country, the consignment may be returned, destroyed, or in some cases, the consignment may undergo some treatment that renders it fit for release.

4. Voluntary Sustainability Standards

Certifications such as Fair Trade, Organic, and Rainforest Alliance set criteria for sustainable farming practices, enhancing marketability and ensuring adherence to environmental and social standards. The case study mentioned Voluntary Sustainability Standards, such as Fair Trade, Organic, Rainforest Alliance, and UTZ-Certified. These certifications enhance the marketability of coffee by ensuring adherence to environmental and social standards, appealing to ethically conscious consumers in the EU and other markets.

Impact of Trade between Countries and the European Union

The legal frameworks in Uganda and Tanzania, combined with international agreements, significantly impact trade dynamics with the European Union:

- *Market Access and Trade Facilitation:* Compliance with EU regulations on food safety and quality (e.g., Regulation EC No 178/2002, EC No 852/2004) ensures that coffee exports from Uganda and Tanzania meet the stringent requirements of the EU market, facilitating smoother market access and boosting trade volumes.
- *Preferential Trade Agreements:* Under the Everything but Arms (EBA) scheme, Least Developed Countries like Uganda and Tanzania enjoy duty-free and quota-free access to the EU market. This preferential treatment enhances the competitiveness of their coffee exports in the European market.
- *Sustainability Standards and Certifications:* Adherence to voluntary sustainability standards (Fair Trade, Organic) enhances the appeal of Ugandan and Tanzanian coffee in the EU market, where consumers are increasingly prioritising ethically sourced and environmentally sustainable products.
- *Economic Partnership Agreements (EPAs):* Although not specifically addressed in detail, EPAs can potentially influence trade terms and conditions, including tariffs, quotas, and trade facilitation measures, impacting coffee exports to the EU.

Unaddressed Areas of Law

The case study highlights several areas where the legal framework is lacking or insufficiently addressed:

- *Intellectual Property Rights:* There is minimal mention of IP laws despite their importance in protecting innovations and ensuring fair competition in the coffee sector.
- *Gender Equality:* There is a lack of gender-responsive policies within the agricultural legal frameworks. This is crucial for promoting inclusive growth and ensuring that both men and women benefit equally from agricultural development.
- *Human Rights:* While human rights are briefly mentioned, there is no detailed reference to specific domestic laws or international frameworks addressing human rights protections within the agricultural sector.

- *Environmental Laws Beyond EIA:* The focus is primarily on EIA, with limited mention of other environmental regulations that could impact sustainable agricultural practices and biodiversity conservation.
- *Comprehensive Labour Laws:* Although some aspects of labour law are covered, more comprehensive regulations are needed to address all facets of worker rights, including those specific to seasonal and migrant agricultural workers.

Final Remarks

The legal framework encompassing international agreements, regional trade pacts, and domestic laws in Uganda and Tanzania is critical in shaping the agricultural sector, particularly the coffee industry. These laws impact everything from production practices to market access and trade facilitation with the European Union. Also, the integration of SDGs into the agricultural policies and practices in Uganda and Tanzania significantly impacts the sustainability and marketability of their coffee industries. These countries enhance their trade relationships with the European Union by aligning with international standards and promoting sustainable practices. However, to fully capitalise on these opportunities, it is crucial to address existing gaps in intellectual property rights, gender equality, comprehensive human rights, and labour protections. Strengthening these areas will ensure a more inclusive, sustainable, and competitive agricultural sector.

Case Study #2

Intra-EU trade, resilience and social sustainability: the case of the oats value chain in the Nordics

Lead organisation & name of lead contact: University of Helsinki; Bodo Steiner

Introduction

The Report "Intra-EU Trade Resilience and Social Sustainability: The Case of the Oats Value Chain in the Nordics" explores the social and environmental sustainability within the oats value chains of Finland and Sweden, focusing on intra-EU trade. The legal framework involves domestic laws, European Union regulations, and international agreements, collectively shaping this sector's operations and trade activities.

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

The case study integrates several SDGs, specifically SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), SDG 13 (Climate Action), and SDG 15 (Life on Land).

- **SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth):** The focus on fair wages, safe working conditions, and equitable labour practices aligns with SDG 8. The legal framework supports these goals through robust labour laws and compliance with ILO conventions. The report highlights efforts to ensure fair wages and safe working conditions, aligning with SDG 8. The legal framework supports decent work and economic growth by ensuring fair labour practices and job security.
- **SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production):** EU regulations on food safety, organic production, and waste reduction promote sustainable consumption and production patterns. The legal framework encourages efficient resource use and sustainable agricultural practices, contributing to SDG 12. It emphasises sustainable production practices and efficient resource use. The report discusses sustainable farming practices. EU regulations promote responsible consumption and production, contributing to sustainable agriculture in the oats value chain.

- **SDG 13 (Climate Action):** Climate action policies and international agreements like the Paris Agreement drive efforts to combat climate change in agriculture. These regulations promote climate-resilient farming practices, aligning with SDG 13. Focuses on reducing greenhouse gas emissions and adopting climate-resilient practices. The report mentions efforts to reduce emissions from oats farming. Supports climate action goals by encouraging sustainable agricultural practices that reduce the carbon footprint.
- **SDG 15 (Life on Land):** Sustainable management of land and natural resources is crucial for achieving SDG 15. The legal framework, including the CAP and national agricultural laws, supports biodiversity conservation and sustainable land use. This SDG focuses on the sustainable management of land and natural resources. The report highlights efforts to protect biodiversity and soil health. The legal framework supports sustainable land management practices, contributing to biodiversity conservation and environmental sustainability.

Legal Instruments

1. Domestic Legislation

- *Finnish Agricultural Law*

Finnish agriculture is predominantly family-owned, with regulations supporting small to medium-sized farms. Finnish laws emphasise sustainable agricultural practices, including managing natural resources and environmental protection. The Act emphasises the sustainable use of soil, water, and other natural resources in agricultural practices. The report highlights how Finnish farmers adopt sustainable practices to ensure long-term productivity and environmental protection. It also ensures that oats farming in Finland is environmentally sustainable, improving soil health and water quality, which aligns with the EU's environmental standards and boosts marketability.

- *Swedish Agricultural Law*

Similar to Finland, Swedish agricultural policies prioritise sustainability, resource efficiency, and rural development. Sweden has stringent regulations on the use of pesticides and fertilisers to ensure environmental protection. Article 7 (Environmental Protection and Resource Efficiency) focuses on minimising the environmental impact of agricultural activities. The report notes Sweden's stringent regulations on pesticide and fertiliser use to protect the environment. It supports the sustainable production

of oats, meets EU requirements for reduced chemical usage and promotes eco-friendly practices that appeal to EU consumers.

- *Labor Laws*

Finland and Sweden have robust labour laws ensuring fair wages, safe working conditions, and workers' rights, which are critical for maintaining social sustainability in the oats value chain. For instance, Finland's Employment Contracts Act and Sweden's Employment Protection Act provide comprehensive frameworks for labour rights.

- *Finnish Employment Contracts Act*

The Act ensures fair wages and working conditions for agricultural workers. The report emphasises the importance of fair labour practices in maintaining social sustainability. It contributes to the social sustainability of the oats value chain by ensuring decent work conditions, which are critical for domestic stability and international trade relations.

- *Swedish Employment Protection Act*

In the Swedish Employment Protection Act, the report focuses on Article 6 (Employment Security), through which the Act provides protections against unfair dismissal and ensures job security. The report highlights the role of secure employment in enhancing worker productivity and satisfaction. It ensures labour rights are respected, enhancing the social image of Swedish oats in the EU market and supporting fair trade practices.

2. European Union Framework

- *Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)*

The CAP is central to EU agricultural law, providing subsidies and financial support to farmers while promoting sustainable agriculture and rural development. The CAP emphasises environmental protection, sustainable farming practices, and equitable social standards. More importantly, it focuses on CAP's goal to increase agricultural productivity, ensure a fair standard of living for the agricultural community, stabilise markets, assure the availability of supplies, and ensure reasonable prices for consumers. The report also discusses how CAP subsidies support Finnish and Swedish farmers. Finally, the CAP provides financial stability and encourages sustainable farming practices, making Nordic oats competitive in the EU market.

- **General Food Law Regulation (EC 178/2002)**

This regulation ensures food safety and traceability within the EU, impacting how oats are produced, processed, and traded. It sets the groundwork for risk assessment and management in the food supply chain. In particular, the report notes the issue of 'traceability,' requiring the ability to trace food, feed, and ingredients through all production, processing, and distribution stages. The report mentions the importance of traceability for food safety. It ensures that oats produced in Finland and Sweden can be traced back to their origin, enhancing consumer confidence and meeting EU food safety standards.

- *Regulation on Organic Production and Labelling of Organic Products (EU 2018/848)*

This regulation affects organic oats production, ensuring products meet high environmental and animal welfare standards. It establishes high standards for organic production and labelling. The report highlights the growing market for organic oats in the EU. It also helps Nordic farmers gain access to the lucrative organic market by meeting stringent organic production standards and increasing trade opportunities.

- *EU Climate Action Policies*

Regulations such as the EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) and the Effort Sharing Regulation aim to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, impacting agricultural practices and promoting climate-resilient farming (European Commission, 2021). The policies set a cap on greenhouse gas emissions for sectors covered by the system, including agriculture. The report discusses efforts to reduce emissions from oats production. Encourages farmers to adopt climate-friendly practices, aligning with EU climate goals and making their products more attractive to environmentally conscious consumers.

3. International Agreements

- *Paris Agreement*

This international treaty aims to limit global warming by reducing greenhouse gas emissions. The commitments under this agreement influence national policies in Finland and Sweden, promoting sustainable agricultural practices and climate-resilient farming. The agreement seeks to limit global temperature increases and enhance adaptive capacity. The report highlights efforts by Nordic countries to reduce agricultural emissions. Supports the adoption of climate-resilient practices in oats farming, contributing to global climate goals and enhancing the sustainability profile of Nordic oats.

- *International Labour Organization (ILO) Conventions*

Finland and Sweden are signatories to various ILO conventions that protect labour rights, ensuring decent work conditions and social sustainability in the agricultural sector (ILO, 2019). In particular, it refers to Convention No. 87 (*Freedom of Association and Protection of the Right to Organise*). It guarantees the rights of workers to form and join unions. The report mentions the role of labour unions in advocating for better working conditions. Ensures agricultural workers in Finland and Sweden have the right to organise and promote fair labour practices and social sustainability.

Impact on Activities and Trade

1. Social Sustainability

The report highlights the importance of social sustainability in the oats value chain, addressing issues such as market transparency, labour conditions, and fair pricing. Compliance with domestic labour laws and ILO conventions ensures fair wages and safe working conditions, which are essential for social sustainability.

The CAP and EU regulations on food safety and organic production enhance the quality and safety of oats, making them competitive in the EU market. These regulations also support sustainable practices that improve the resilience of the oats value chain against economic and environmental changes.

The specific legal provisions support fair labour practices, safe working conditions, and fair wages, which are essential for social sustainability. Compliance with labour laws and ILO conventions ensures decent work conditions, enhancing the oats value chain's social image and supporting fair trade practices.

2. Environmental Sustainability

EU climate action policies and international agreements like the Paris Agreement drive the adoption of sustainable farming practices. These regulations aim to reduce the carbon footprint of agricultural activities, promoting climate-resilient and environmentally friendly farming.

The legal provisions encourage sustainable farming practices, such as reduced chemical usage, improved resource efficiency, and climate-resilient agriculture. These practices align with EU and international standards, enhancing the environmental sustainability of oats farming in the Nordic countries.

Trade Between Nordic Countries and the EU

- **Market Access and Competitiveness:** EU regulations such as the CAP provide financial support to farmers in Finland and Sweden, enhancing their competitiveness in the EU market. Removing tariffs under the EU-Canada CETA agreement also affects the competitiveness of EU-produced oats. CAP subsidies and compliance with EU regulations on food safety, traceability, and organic production improve the marketability of Nordic oats. These measures ensure that oats from Finland and Sweden meet high-quality standards, facilitating trade within the EU.
- **Sustainability Standards:** Compliance with EU sustainability standards, such as those outlined in the General Food Law Regulation and the Organic Production Regulation, ensures that oats from Finland and Sweden meet high-quality standards, facilitating trade within the EU. Adherence to EU sustainability standards enhances the reputation of Nordic oats as high-quality, environmentally friendly products, increasing their competitiveness in the EU market.
- **Transparency and Fair Pricing:** The report identifies a need for greater market transparency regarding prices and sustainability data. EU regulations promoting transparency and fair competition help address these issues, fostering a more equitable trading environment. The emphasis on traceability and market transparency helps build consumer trust and ensures fair pricing, fostering a more equitable trading environment.

Unaddressed Areas of Law

These areas are covered, but not extensively. In each, some topics are not specifically addressed:

- **Intellectual Property Rights (IPR):** The report does not address intellectual property rights related to agricultural innovations and plant varieties.
- **Trade Secret Protection:** There is no discussion on protecting trade secrets and confidential business information within the oats value chain.
- **Consumer Protection Laws:** While food safety is covered, broader consumer protection laws and their impact on the oats value chain are not discussed.
- **Competition Law:** The report mentions market transparency but does not delve into competition law and its enforcement within the oats value chain.

Final Remarks

The legal framework governing the Nordic oats value chain, encompassing domestic, EU, and international laws, significantly shapes social and environmental sustainability practices. Compliance with labour laws, EU regulations, and international agreements ensures fair wages, safe working conditions, and sustainable farming practices, contributing to resilient intra-EU trade. The integration of SDGs further enhances the sustainability of the oats value chain, promoting responsible consumption, climate action, and biodiversity conservation. However, gaps in addressing intellectual property rights, trade secret protection, consumer protection laws, and competition law suggest areas for further exploration to fully support the sustainability and resilience of the oats value chain.

Case Study #3

Trade, sustainability and environmental linkages in Finnish dairy production

Lead organization & name of lead contact: University of Helsinki, Nina Hyytiä

Introduction

This analysis examines the legal framework within which the case study on Finnish dairy production operates. It assesses the impact of domestic, European, and international laws on the activities studied, discusses how the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are treated, and evaluates the implications for trade between Finland and the European Union (EU). This analysis focuses on the specific articles of the legal instruments mentioned in the report on Finnish dairy production and explains how each is contextualized within the study. Additionally, the analysis identifies areas of law not addressed in the report. This approach will provide a deeper understanding of the legal framework and its impact on dairy activities and trade.

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

The report ties the objectives of Finnish dairy production to various SDGs, mainly focusing on SDG13 and SDG15 through measures to reduce emissions and promote sustainable land use. These SDGs are discussed concerning their alignment with Finnish dairy production goals. The case study uses these goals to frame dairy practices' environmental, economic, and social sustainability, emphasizing how adherence to these goals impacts domestic policies and international trade competitiveness.

The case study explicitly aligns Finnish dairy production with several SDGs, reflecting a commitment to sustainability:

- **SDG 1 (No Poverty):** The report highlights how CAP subsidies and rural development funds support the financial stability of dairy farmers, contributing to poverty reduction in rural areas.

- **SDG 2 (Zero Hunger):** The case study addresses food security and nutritional quality by promoting sustainable dairy farming practices, essential for achieving zero hunger. Sustainable dairy farming practices contribute to food security by ensuring a stable supply of dairy products.
- **SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being):** Ensuring high standards of animal health and food safety directly impacts public health and well-being.
- **SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation):** Sustainable farming practices reduce water pollution, aligning with goals for clean water. Practices to reduce water pollution from dairy farms align with the goals of clean water and sanitation.
- **SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth):** CAP subsidies and rural development programs create job opportunities and promote economic growth in rural areas.
- **SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production):** Emphasizes sustainable production practices, reducing the environmental impact of dairy farming.
- **SDG 13 (Climate Action):** The report discusses efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from dairy farming, contributing to climate action goals (p. 17). Efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from dairy farming contribute to climate action goals. The report's focus on carbon taxation and emission reductions addresses climate change.
- **SDG 15 (Life on Land):** Practices that prevent deforestation and promote biodiversity are critical for sustaining life on land. The dairy industry supports biodiversity and ecosystem health by promoting sustainable land use and reducing nutrient leakages.

Legal Instruments

The case study mentions various legal instruments that influence Finnish dairy production. Below is an examination of each mentioned legislation and its context:

1. Domestic Legislation

- *Act on the Management of the Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy (1324/2022)*

This Act ensures the alignment of Finland's agricultural policies with the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). It discusses the Act's role in aligning Finnish agricultural

policy with the EU's CAP. There are critical provisions in the Act, including those on planning, implementing, and monitoring agricultural activities. This Act aims to ensure that Finnish agricultural practices, including dairy, meet the sustainability goals and funding structures set forth by the EU's CAP. The Act is crucial for ensuring Finnish dairy farmers comply with the CAP requirements and promote sustainability and efficient resource use. It ensures coordinated management of agricultural policies to align with EU objectives.

- *Act on European Union Direct Farmer Subsidies (1332/2022)*

The Act outlines the distribution of direct payments to farmers, emphasizing sustainable farming practices and environmental measures. This legislation provides financial stability to dairy farmers, encouraging practices that enhance environmental sustainability, such as reducing greenhouse gas emissions and protecting biodiversity. It also specifies the distribution of direct payments to farmers, emphasizing sustainable practices. The report discusses this Act in the context of financial support to dairy farmers, which helps them maintain sustainable practices in line with EU standards.

- *Act on Rural Development Compensations (1333/2022)*

This legal instrument supports rural development through financial compensations, focusing on maintaining rural viability. These compensations help dairy farmers invest in sustainable technologies and practices, foster rural development, and ensure rural communities' economic stability. The Act specifies compensations for rural development projects, targeting economic viability and environmental sustainability. It also details compensations for rural development projects. Supports dairy farmers by providing financial aid for sustainable development projects.

- *Act on the Implementation of Certain European Union and National Agricultural Subsidies (1334/2022)*

The Act manages distributing and regulating agricultural subsidies from the EU and national sources. It guarantees dairy farmers receive subsidies supporting environmentally friendly practices and innovations in farming.

- *Act on Reindeer Farming (986/2011)*

This Act regulates reindeer farming practices, including sustainability measures and market practices. Although focused on reindeer farming, it impacts broader agricultural practices in northern regions, including dairy farming, promoting

sustainable land use and animal welfare. It promotes sustainable land use and animal welfare, with specific articles detailing reindeer farm management and environmental considerations.

- *Act on the Market Organization of Agricultural Products (999/2012)*

The legislation governs the market organization for agricultural products, ensuring fair trade practices. It affects the dairy market by ensuring fair trade practices, market stability, and proper pricing mechanisms, which are crucial for the economic viability of dairy farms.

- *Act on Supporting Rural Development in the Funding Period 2023–2027 (1325/2022)*

The Act focuses on rural development initiatives and funding allocations, including funding and support measures for rural development projects during the specified period. It supports dairy farmers in rural areas by providing necessary funding for development projects. It provides essential funding for dairy farmers to invest in sustainable practices and technologies, thus supporting the long-term development of rural areas.

- *Act on Agricultural Structures (1476/2007)*

This Act regulates the structural organization of agriculture, including sustainability and modernization measures. It also encourages modernization to improve the efficiency and sustainability of dairy farms, including infrastructure upgrades and adoption of new technologies, and support for adopting new technologies.

- *Law on Identification and Registration of Animals (1069/2021)*

The Law mandates the identification and registration of livestock for traceability. It enhances traceability in the dairy sector, improving food safety and disease control, which is critical for maintaining high standards in dairy production.

- *Animal Diseases Act (76/2021)*

The Act regulates measures for controlling animal diseases. It is essential for managing health risks in the dairy industry, ensuring herd health and product safety. Moreover, it ensures herd health and biosecurity in dairy farms, contributing to the overall public health and safety of dairy products.

- *Animal Protection Act (247/1996)*

The Animal Protection Act establishes standards for animal welfare. Influences dairy farming practices by enforcing high animal welfare standards, ensuring ethical treatment of dairy cattle. This Act is mentioned in relation to its impact on improving animal welfare standards across Finnish dairy farms, influencing both domestic policies and market perceptions within the EU.

- *Animal Transport Act (1429/2006)*

This Act regulates the transport conditions of animals. It guarantees the humane transport of dairy cattle, impacting logistics and operational practices. Finally, it ensures the humane transport of dairy cattle, impacting logistics and operational practices in the dairy industry.

- *Government Decree 592/2010 on the Protection of Cattle*

The decree provides specific protection measures for cattle and sets standards for the housing and care of dairy cattle, impacting farm management. It specifies protective measures for cattle and standards for the housing and care of dairy cattle, impacting farm management and animal welfare practices.

1. European Framework

- *EU Regulation 1308/2013*

The Regulation establishes a common organization of the markets in agricultural products. Governs the market dynamics for dairy products within the EU, ensuring fair competition and market stability. This Regulation is referred to in terms of its role in organizing the market for agricultural products, which directly affects how dairy products are traded and priced within the EU.

- *European Green Deal*

It aims to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050. It includes policies on biodiversity, agriculture, and food security. The report discusses how the European Green Deal influences Finnish agricultural policies, particularly the emphasis on reducing greenhouse gas emissions from dairy production and promoting sustainable practices in dairy farming.

- *Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)*

CAP provides financial support to farmers within the EU, emphasizing environmental sustainability, rural development, and food security. The CAP is mentioned in relation to subsidies and incentives that impact Finnish dairy farmers, guiding their practices towards more sustainable methods.

- *European Green Deal*

The Green Deal is referenced broadly as influencing Finnish dairy production through its overarching climate goals, which include reducing emissions and promoting sustainable agricultural practices.

- *CAP European Green Deal Agenda 2023*

The report shows the CAP's integration with the Green Deal's objectives. This integration is contextualized as driving the transition towards sustainable agricultural practices, particularly in dairy farming, to achieve climate neutrality. Provides financial support and regulatory frameworks for EU farmers, focusing on environmental sustainability, rural development, and food security. The CAP impacts Finnish dairy farmers by offering subsidies and incentives for sustainable farming practices and rural development projects.

- *Emission Trading System (ETS)*

This is a market-based approach to controlling pollution by providing economic incentives for reducing emissions. The ETS impacts dairy production by imposing carbon taxes and encouraging practices that reduce greenhouse gas emissions, aligning with broader climate goals.

- *Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM)*

It aims to prevent carbon leakage by imposing carbon tariffs on imports from countries with less stringent climate policies. CBAM impacts the competitiveness of Finnish dairy exports, ensuring that imports into the EU meet environmental standards, thus maintaining a level playing field.

- *EU Deforestation Regulation*

The EU Deforestation Regulation prohibits agricultural production that leads to deforestation, including dairy-related activities. This Regulation poses challenges for new dairy farm constructions and expansions, requiring compliance with anti-

deforestation measures to receive subsidies. This challenges new dairy farm constructions, as compliance with deforestation regulations is required.

- *EU Animal Health Law (Regulation 2016/429)*

This is a comprehensive regulation of animal health, including disease prevention and control measures. Ensures the health and biosecurity of dairy herds, impacting farm management practices and aligning with EU standards for animal health. It impacts various regulations concerning hygiene, animal products, and health certificates. These regulations ensure that Finnish dairy products meet high safety and health standards, which are essential for trade within the EU.

- *EU Regulation 2019/624*

It concerns the official controls on products of animal origin. The Regulation ensures that Finnish dairy products meet high standards for hygiene and safety, which is crucial for trade within the EU.

- *EU Regulation 2019/625*

This Regulation specifies requirements for the entry into the Union of consignments of certain animals and goods intended for human consumption. It ensures that imports of dairy products meet stringent safety and quality standards, impacting export practices. Articles outline the conditions for entry and the necessary certifications.

- *EU Regulation 2019/627*

This legal instrument lays down uniform practical arrangements for the performance of official controls on products of animal origin. It impacts dairy product inspection and control processes, ensuring compliance with EU standards. Moreover, it also lays down uniform practical arrangements for the performance of official controls on products of animal origin, therefore also impacting dairy product inspection and control processes, ensuring compliance with EU standards.

- *EU Regulation 2020/2235*

Such regulation concerns certification and official controls of animals and goods to ensure compliance with animal health and welfare standards. It affects the certification processes for Finnish dairy products, ensuring they meet EU animal health and welfare standards.

- *EU Regulation 2021/405*

Regulation 2021 establishes a list of third countries and regions from which imports of certain animals and products are permitted. It also regulates the importation of dairy products, ensuring they meet EU standards, impacting trade practices and market access.

2. International Framework

- *WTO Sanitary and Phytosanitary (SPS) Agreement*

The agreement guarantees that food safety and animal and plant health regulations are based on scientific principles. The agreement affects how Finnish dairy products meet international safety standards, facilitating global trade. The case study report discusses the SPS Agreement in the broader context of how it regulates international dairy trade, ensuring that Finnish dairy products meet global health and safety standards.

- *WTO Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT) Agreement*

This agreement aims to ensure that technical regulations, standards, and conformity assessments do not create unnecessary obstacles to trade. It serves to ensure Finnish dairy products comply with technical standards, thereby enhancing their market access. This agreement is referenced in terms of setting technical standards for trade, which influences how Finnish dairy products are produced and labelled to meet international trade standards.

- *WTO Agreement on Agriculture (AoA)*

The Agreement on Agriculture focuses on market access, domestic support, and export subsidies in the agricultural sector. It influences Finnish dairy production by setting international trade standards, ensuring that practices align with global trade rules.

- *Paris Agreement*

The Paris Agreement is an international treaty on climate change aiming to limit global warming to well below 2 degrees Celsius. It impacts dairy farming by promoting practices that reduce greenhouse gas emissions, aligning with global climate goals.

- *Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)*

The CBD's main objective is to conserve biological diversity, promote sustainable use of its components, and ensure fair and equitable benefits-sharing. Influences sustainable farming practices that protect biodiversity in dairy production.

- *International Plant Protection Convention (IPPC)*

This convention aims to prevent the spread of pests in plants and plant products. It ensures that dairy farming practices do not contribute to spreading pests, maintaining plant health and sustainability.

- *Codex Alimentarius*

The Codex Alimentarius sets out international food standards, guidelines, and codes of practice to ensure food safety and quality. It also sets the standards for the safety and quality of dairy products, impacting production and trade practices.

Impact of Legal Instruments on Dairy Production

1. Domestic Impact

- *Carbon Taxation:* Imposing carbon taxes on agricultural emissions significantly affects dairy production costs. The report's scenarios show how different tax levels impact outputs, incomes, and emissions.
- *Subsidies and Incentives:* CAP payments based on environmental measures incentivize sustainable practices and create financial dependencies on subsidies.

2. European Impact

- *Green Deal Compliance:* Finnish dairy producers must adhere to stringent environmental standards set by the European Green Deal, impacting operational practices and potentially increasing costs.
- *Trade Regulations:* Compliance with EU trade regulations, such as the SPS and TBT agreements, ensures that Finnish dairy products meet high standards, affecting their competitiveness in the EU market.

3. International Impact

- *Global Competitiveness*: The WTO agreements, including SPS and TBT, affect how Finnish dairy products are perceived internationally. Adhering to these standards can enhance market access and impose compliance costs.

Impact on Trade

1. Intra-EU Trade

- *Regulatory Compliance*: Finnish dairy products must meet EU standards, which can be both a barrier and a market guarantee, affecting trade volumes and market access within the EU.

2. Extra-EU Trade

- *Competitive Edge*: High standards and compliance with international trade agreements can enhance the reputation of Finnish dairy products, potentially opening new markets.

The legal framework and adherence to SDGs have significant implications for trade between Finland and the EU:

- *Enhanced Market Access*: Compliance with EU regulations and international standards ensures that Finnish dairy products can be traded within the EU and globally without barriers.
- *Competitiveness*: CAP subsidies and sustainable practices improve the competitiveness of Finnish dairy products in the EU market.
- *Environmental Standards*: Adherence to environmental regulations, such as the EU Deforestation Regulation, ensures that Finnish dairy products meet the high environmental standards demanded by EU consumers.

Unaddressed Areas of Law

These areas are covered, but not extensively. In each, some topics are not specifically addressed:

- *Animal Welfare Laws*: Specific regulations related to animal welfare, which could impact dairy farming practices and trade, are not detailed.

- *Food Safety Standards:* While trade-related standards are mentioned, specific food safety laws at the national and EU levels are not thoroughly analyzed.
- *Intellectual Property Rights (IPR):* Regulations concerning agricultural innovations and trademarks protection.
- *Labour Laws:* There is no detailed analysis of labour conditions and protections for farm workers.
- *Data Privacy:* Regulations on handling farm data, particularly in the context of digital farming technologies.

Final Remarks

The legal framework governing Finnish dairy production is comprehensive, covering various domestic, European, and international laws. These regulations impact farm management practices and align with various SDGs, promoting sustainability and economic growth. The framework ensures that Finnish dairy products meet high standards, facilitating trade within the EU and globally. The case study integrates a variety of legal instruments, focusing on their broader impact on Finnish dairy production and trade. Future analyses could benefit from a more granular exploration of these legal documents to fully understand their specific provisions and implications.

Moreover, additional areas such as IPR, labour laws, and data privacy could be further explored to provide a more holistic understanding of the legal environment. The case study shows the dual impact of regulatory compliance on enhancing trade competitiveness and imposing operational challenges. Finally, future research could benefit from a more detailed examination of animal welfare laws and food safety standards, which are crucial for comprehensive legal compliance and trade facilitation.

Case Study #4

Enhancing Access to Export Markets by Sub Saharan African (SSA) Countries through Sustainable Investments to Ensure Quality of Agri-food Commodities: The cases of Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana

Lead organisation & name of lead contact: Dr Hoseana Bohela Lunogelo, Dr Daniel Ngowi, and Prof Deus Rwehumbiza.

Analysis of the Legal Framework in the Case Study

Introduction

The legal framework analysis surrounding the case study "Enhancing Access to Export Markets by Sub-Saharan African Countries through Sustainable Investments to Ensure Quality and Quantity of Agri-food Commodities" encompasses several domestic, European, and international legal instruments. These instruments play critical roles in facilitating the export of agricultural products from Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana to the European Union and other global markets. The instruments identified focus on improving these countries' agricultural exports to the European Union (EU) through sustainable practices. This analysis focuses on specific legal instruments mentioned in the case study, assessing their impact on trade and identifying legal gaps.

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

The case study emphasises the alignment of agricultural activities in Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana with key Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The focus on SDG 1 (No Poverty), SDG 2 (Zero Hunger), SDG 13 (Climate Action), and SDG 15 (Life on Land) highlights the critical role of sustainable agricultural practices in achieving both local socio-economic improvements and meeting international trade requirements, particularly in the European Union (EU).

- **SDG 1 (No Poverty):** Agricultural commodities contribute to income generation, reducing poverty among small-scale farmers. The case study highlights the role of selected agri-food commodities in generating income for rural households, constituting a significant portion of the population in the studied

countries. For instance, Uganda's banana production and Ghana's cocoa industry are crucial in lifting small-scale farmers out of poverty. The income generated through these commodities enhances the economic stability of rural communities, making them viable trade partners for the EU. Increased household incomes also lead to better investment in agricultural inputs, improving the quality and quantity of exports, thus aligning with EU standards.

- **SDG 2 (Zero Hunger):** Enhances food security and nutrition through sustainable agricultural practices. The report stresses that the selected commodities contribute to income and improve food security by providing nutritious food. For example, Ethiopia's goat meat contributes to food security by offering a reliable source of protein for local communities. Ensuring food security through sustainable agricultural practices builds resilience within the agricultural sector. This, in turn, leads to more consistent and reliable exports, which is critical for maintaining trade relations with the EU, where food safety and quality are highly regulated.
- **SDG 13 (Climate Action):** Promotes climate-friendly agricultural practices, aligning with international climate agreements. Promoting Good Agricultural Practices (GAP) under SDG 13 is crucial for mitigating climate change. The study notes that Uganda's banana farming practices and Ethiopia's goat meat production incorporate climate-smart strategies that minimise environmental impact. By adopting climate-resilient agricultural practices, these countries enhance their export products' appeal to the EU, with a growing demand for products with lower carbon footprints. Additionally, compliance with international environmental agreements bolsters these countries' positions in global markets.
- **SDG 15 (Life on Land):** Encourages sustainable land use and biodiversity conservation through Good Agricultural Practices (GAP). The SDG 15 initiatives focus on sustainable land management and biodiversity preservation. For instance, Tanzania's cassava production and Uganda's banana farming are encouraged to use sustainable practices that prevent land degradation and promote reforestation. Sustainable land use ensures the long-term viability of agricultural exports, which is critical for meeting EU import standards that prioritise environmental sustainability. Adopting practices that conserve biodiversity and mitigate deforestation is increasingly becoming a non-tariff requirement for access to European markets.

Legal Instruments

The legal framework within which the case study on enhancing access to export markets by Sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries (Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana) through sustainable investments involves various domestic, European, and international laws and regulations. These legal instruments significantly impact the activities studied in the report, mainly concerning agricultural trade, sustainability, and compliance with international standards.

1. Domestic Legislation

Tanzania

- *Environmental Management Act (2004)*

The act governs environmental protection and management, impacting agricultural practices by enforcing sustainable farming techniques. The report discusses how Tanzania's Environmental Management Act influences sustainable agricultural practices. While specific articles are not directly referenced, this Act generally sets standards for environmental protection that affect agricultural activities. No specific articles were mentioned, but this Act generally governs environmental protection and management, influencing sustainable agricultural practices.

- *Plant Protection Act (1997)*

This Act regulates plant health and pest control, ensuring the quality of agricultural products for export. This Act is relevant for controlling pests and diseases affecting plants. The case study implies that adherence to this law is crucial for ensuring the quality of agri-food products for export, though specific articles need to be more detailed.

Uganda

- *Employment Act 2006*

The Act regulates employment practices, influencing labour standards in agriculture. The report discusses how this article ensures fair labour practices in the agricultural sector, affecting the overall working conditions in Uganda's export-oriented agricultural industries. It references the need to provide for regulations for employment standards.

- *Plant Protection and Health Act 2015*

This Act aims to prevent the introduction and spread of pests and diseases destructive to plants, regulate the introduction of exotic plants and microorganisms, and enforce control over the importation and exportation of articles that can spread diseases or pests. This Act focuses on preventing the introduction and spread of plant pests and diseases, mainly through regulating the importation and exportation of plants and microorganisms. By ensuring compliance with international phytosanitary standards, this law helps Uganda's agricultural exports meet the stringent requirements of the EU, reducing the risk of trade disruptions. It references the need to prevent the introduction and spread of pests and diseases. The case study highlights how Uganda's Plant Protection and Health Act is essential for maintaining the health of crops, which impacts the quality and safety of agricultural exports. It also regulates the introduction of exotic plants and microorganisms. Ensuring new plants and microorganisms do not introduce pests or diseases is critical for protecting Uganda's agricultural sector and facilitating trade. This legislation ensures that Uganda's agricultural exports, such as bananas, meet the phytosanitary standards required by the EU, reducing barriers to entry and enhancing market access.

- *Food and Drug Act Cap 278*

The Act establishes food and drug safety standards, addressing offences related to preparing and selling injurious foods and adulterated drugs. This law supports Uganda's compliance with EU food safety regulations, facilitating exporting of food products to European markets. In particular, it concentrates on establishing food and drug safety standards. This article is crucial for ensuring food products meet safety standards before export, affecting Uganda's trade with international markets. Compliance with this Act is critical for ensuring that food products exported from Uganda to the EU meet international health and safety.

- *Investment Code Act 2019*

The Act governs the investment landscape, with the Uganda Investment Authority (UIA) being the central agency responsible for attracting and facilitating investments. The act governs investments, with the Uganda Investment Authority (UIA) responsible for promoting, attracting, and facilitating investments in the country. This Act creates a stable and conducive environment for foreign investments, including those targeting agricultural exports, enhancing and boosting the competitiveness and export of Uganda's commodities in the EU market. In particular, it is essential to note that Article 10 defines the role of the Uganda Investment Authority in promoting and

regulating investments. The report mentions this article to show how Uganda's Investment Code Act facilitates agricultural investment, which is necessary for expanding export markets.

- *Occupational Health and Safety Act 2006*

This Act consolidates laws on workplace safety, ensuring that agricultural practices comply with national health standards. The act consolidates and harmonises the law on safety and health, enforcing workplace safety measures. By enforcing workplace safety in agricultural production, this Act helps align Uganda's agricultural practices with the EU's ethical standards, an increasingly important factor in securing market access. It ensures safe agricultural practices align with the ethical and sustainability standards expected by European consumers, thus supporting market access. More specifically, it is crucial to note the Act outlines the general duties of employers to ensure health and safety at workplaces. It guarantees safety in agricultural workplaces, impacts labour conditions and productivity, and influences Uganda's agricultural output and trade.

Ethiopia

- *Environmental Policy*

It focuses on sustainable development and environmental protection, affecting agricultural practices. The report refers to Ethiopia's Environmental Policy in the context of promoting sustainable agricultural practices. The policy emphasises that sustainability impacts the country's agricultural sector and international trade practices.

- *Plant Quarantine Regulations*

Prevents the entry of pests and diseases, ensuring the quality of exports. These regulations prevent the entry of harmful pests and diseases, ensuring that Ethiopian agricultural products meet international standards for export. It ensures the quality of exports by preventing the entry of pests and diseases.

Ghana

- *Plant Protection Act*

Similar to Uganda's, it ensures plant health, which is critical for maintaining export standards. The report refers to Ghana's Plant Protection Act, which ensures agricultural exports are free from pests and diseases. The Act regulates plant health to maintain export standards.

- *Environmental Protection Agency Act*

The Act enforces environmental regulations that affect agricultural sustainability. The report highlights how this Act influences sustainable agricultural practices by enforcing environmental regulations. The Act's general provisions are relevant to agricultural sustainability and trade.

2. International Legal Agreements

- *UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)*

The countries involved have committed to low-carbon development and climate change adaptation measures under the UNFCCC. Aligning with the UNFCCC provisions helps these countries enhance the sustainability of their agricultural practices, which is crucial for meeting the EU's environmental criteria for imports. More specifically, the report refers parties obligations to commit to mitigating climate change and adapting to its effects. The report refers to this article in the context of the countries' commitment to integrating climate-friendly practices in agriculture, impacting their international trade compliance and environmental sustainability.

- *Kyoto Protocol*

Adherence to the Kyoto Protocol strengthens the countries' positions in the EU market by demonstrating a commitment to reducing the carbon footprint of their agricultural exports. This reflects countries' commitments to reducing emissions from agricultural practices, affecting their trade compliance with international climate agreements.

Compliance with these environmental agreements enhances the sustainability credentials of the products from these countries, making them more attractive to EU markets that prioritise green imports.

- *Convention on Biological Diversity*

The Convention emphasises the conservation and sustainable use of biological diversity. By complying with this Convention, the countries ensure that their agricultural exports do not contribute to biodiversity loss, an essential consideration for the EU market. The report references Article 6, which encourages sustainable use of biodiversity, in discussing how adherence to biodiversity conservation contributes to sustainable agricultural practices, impacting trade by ensuring the conservation of genetic resources.

- *Montreal Protocol*

The Protocol aims to phase out ozone-depleting substances that affect agricultural chemical use. The case study refers to Article 2A, phasing out substances that deplete the ozone layer, to highlight how compliance with the Montreal Protocol affects agricultural practices, especially concerning the use of chemicals in farming.

- *Green Climate Fund and Adaptation Fund*

The Fund provides financial resources for climate-related agricultural projects. The report mentions these funds to illustrate how the countries access international financial resources to support climate-resilient agricultural practices, influencing their export potential. In particular, it references Art. 6.2, providing access to financial resources for climate adaptation and mitigation projects.

- *Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards (CREFAA)*

The Convention facilitates recognising and enforcing international arbitral awards, promoting confidence in international investment. In this context, this Convention ensures that trade and investment disputes are resolved efficiently, providing a secure legal environment for international traders and investors in these countries. It promotes confidence in the agricultural sectors of the involved countries, which is vital for securing foreign investment and expanding exports to the EU.

3. WTO and Trade Agreements

These World Trade Organization (WTO) agreements support creating a transparent trade system that benefits the countries studied by ensuring their agricultural exports meet global standards, including those of the EU.

- *Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS)*

The Agreement ensures that intellectual property rights are not barriers to legitimate trade. Compliance with TRIPS is crucial for protecting agricultural innovations and trade secrets, which are increasingly important in the global trade of high-quality agricultural products and can significantly impact the competitiveness of the countries' exports in the EU market. The report also discusses Article 27 to explain how intellectual property protection impacts agricultural innovations and trade.

- *Agreement on Trade-Related Investment Measures (TRIMS)*

Ensure that investment measures do not distort trade, affecting foreign agricultural investments. The report mentions Article 2 on national treatment, which aims to ensure that investment measures do not restrict or distort trade, to explain how adherence to TRIMS promotes fair trade practices and protects investment in the agricultural sector.

- *African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA)*

The Act provides preferential access to the US market. The report references Article 104 to discuss how AGOA supports agricultural exports from the studied countries to the US market.

These trade agreements with the US tariff-free access to these markets directly benefit agricultural exports from the studied countries. Compliance with the provisions under these agreements is crucial for maintaining market access.

4. EU LEGISLATION

- *Everything but Arms (EBA)*

This EU initiative offers duty-free access to the EU market for the studied countries' agricultural products. The initiative directly impacts trade by making these countries' exports more competitive in the EU market. It grants duty-free access to all products, except arms and ammunition, from these countries to the EU. The EBA grants duty-free access to the EU market for all products except arms and ammunition from Least Developed Countries (LDCs). This initiative is particularly advantageous for the studied countries, as it reduces the cost of exporting agricultural products to the EU, enhancing their competitiveness.

- *Generalised System of Preferences (GSP) and Everything but Arms (EBA) initiative with the EU*

The report also refers to GSP's Article 12, which explains how preferential access to EU markets under the GSP and EBA initiatives boost exports from the studied countries.

5. Standards and Compliance

Compliance with these EU and international standards ensures that the agricultural products meet the safety and quality requirements for export to the EU. Adherence to these standards is critical for accessing and maintaining presence in the European markets.

- *Hazard Analysis Critical Control Points (HACCP)*

HACCP involves identifying and managing food safety risks throughout the supply chain. Adherence to HACCP is necessary for ensuring that food products from these countries meet the EU's strict food safety requirements, facilitating smoother market entry.

- *ISO Certifications (ISO 17025, ISO 22000, ISO 9000)*

These certifications ensure laboratory competence, food safety, and quality management. Adherence to these standards is essential for maintaining the high quality and safety levels required by the EU, thereby supporting the export potential of these countries. Ensure compliance with international standards, which is crucial for export quality.

- *ISO 17025*

This standard specifies requirements for laboratory competence. The report mentions this certification to emphasise the importance of reliable testing for agricultural products and general requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories.

- *ISO 22000*

The standard focuses on food safety management systems. The report highlights this certification as crucial for ensuring the safety of food products in international trade. This standard specifies the requirements for a food safety management system.

Compliance with ISO 22000 is critical for accessing the EU market, where food safety standards are paramount. For example, Ugandan bananas exported to the EU must meet these standards to ensure they are safe for consumption.

➤ *ISO 9000*

The ISO 9000 standard provides guidelines for quality management systems. This certification is referenced to ensure that agricultural products meet quality standards for export.

Impact on Trade with the European Union

The alignment of agricultural practices in the studied countries with the above SDGs directly influences their trade relations with the EU. The EU's stringent requirements on environmental sustainability, food safety, and social standards mean that adherence to these SDGs facilitates market access and enhances the competitiveness of these countries' exports.

Adherence and compliance to various international agreements and standards facilitate the trade of agri-food products between the studied countries and the European Union. Compliance with EU regulations, such as the GSP and EBA, ensures that these countries can export their products duty-free, enhancing their competitiveness in the European market. For instance, the Everything but Arms initiative provides a significant competitive advantage by offering duty-free access to the EU market. The alignment with ISO and HACCP standards and compliance with EU sanitary and phytosanitary measures are crucial for maintaining export quality and meeting the stringent requirements of the European market. This remains critical for sustaining and expanding market access. By complying with international agreements like TRIPS, GATS, and environmental protocols, the countries are better positioned to access the European market. The EBA initiative further facilitates this access by removing tariffs on agricultural products, a significant export for these countries. However, compliance with stringent EU standards on food safety, environmental sustainability, and labour rights remains challenging and requires continuous investment and capacity building. Additionally, aligning with international environmental and trade agreements, like the UNFCCC and TRIPS, enhances the sustainability and intellectual property protections that European consumers and regulators increasingly demand.

However, the complexity of complying with these diverse legal requirements poses a challenge, especially for small-scale producers, highlighting the need for continuous capacity building and institutional support.

Unaddressed Areas of Law

While the report covers a broad range of legal frameworks, certain areas could be further explored:

- *Intellectual Property Rights:* Insufficiently detailed provisions protect agricultural innovations and plant varieties. Although the TRIPS agreement is mentioned, there is insufficient discussion on how intellectual property rights, particularly regarding agricultural innovations and biotechnology, impact trade and investment in the studied countries.
- *Trade Facilitation Agreements:* The report does not discuss specific agreements that streamline customs procedures and reduce trade barriers.
- *Labor Rights and Social Protections in Agriculture:* It would be appropriate to have a more comprehensive analysis of labour laws and their enforcement in the agricultural sector. While the report mentions compliance with domestic labour laws, there is limited discussion on the broader implications of international labour standards on trade, such as those established by the International Labour Organization (ILO). A more detailed analysis of how these standards impact the agricultural value chains would be beneficial, especially those related to child labour in the agricultural sector.
- *Data Privacy:* There is not enough information on regulations concerning the handling of agricultural data, especially in international trade contexts.
- *Digital Trade and E-Commerce:* The report does not address the role of digital trade regulations, which are increasingly important in international trade. There is a need to integrate policies that facilitate digital platforms for agricultural exports, particularly as the EU emphasises traceability and digital compliance.
- *Competition Law:* The report does not address competition law, which is critical for ensuring that the domestic markets in these countries remain competitive and attractive to local and foreign investors. The report overlooks the role of competition law, which is vital for ensuring a level playing field in the domestic market, especially as these countries engage more with international trade partners.

Final Remarks

The SDGs mentioned in the case study play a pivotal role in shaping the agricultural activities of the studied countries and their trade relationships with the EU. By focusing on poverty alleviation, food security, climate action, and land sustainability, these countries improve the livelihoods of their rural populations and strengthen their compliance with the EU's stringent import requirements. However, continuous investment in capacity building, infrastructure, and technology is essential to capitalise on these opportunities fully.

The legal framework encompassing domestic, European, and international laws significantly impacts the agricultural activities studied in the case study. While comprehensive, covering a broad spectrum of domestic, European, and international laws that impact agricultural trade. These laws facilitate market access to the EU but impose stringent compliance requirements that the studied countries must continuously meet. These laws ensure sustainable agricultural practices comply with international standards and facilitate trade between the studied countries and the European Union. Addressing the identified legal gaps could further enhance the effectiveness of this framework, particularly in areas like digital trade, labour rights, intellectual property, and competition law. The SDGs are crucial in guiding these practices promoting sustainable development and trade. It reinforces these countries' positions as reliable and sustainable trade partners in the global market, particularly with the EU, which increasingly values sustainability in its trade policies. Addressing the identified gaps in the legal framework could further enhance the effectiveness of these initiatives.

Case Study #5

Role of policy frameworks and social cohesion for sustainable value chains and livelihoods in Ghana

Lead organization & name of lead contact: Technical University of Madrid, Pablo Vidueira

Introduction

The legal framework within which the case study on Ghana's poultry sector operates involves a comprehensive set of domestic laws, European Union regulations, and international agreements. These legal instruments impact the sector's activities and trade dynamics with the European Union and other international partners. This analysis details the specific provisions of each legal instrument and their relevance to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and assesses their impact on the activities studied in the report.

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) provide a global framework for sustainable development, and the case study mentions several SDGs that directly impact the activities analyzed in the report. These SDGs also influence trade between Ghana and the EU.

- **SDG 1: No Poverty:** The poultry sector significantly generates income for rural households, helping alleviate poverty among small-scale farmers. By improving farmers' livelihoods, the sector enhances economic stability and supports poverty reduction efforts. This creates a more robust local economy capable of engaging in international trade, including exports to the EU.
- **SDG 2: Zero Hunger:** The poultry sector is critical in ensuring food security by providing affordable and nutritious food. An enhanced domestic production reduces reliance on imports, improving local food security and nutritional standards. This supports achieving zero hunger, creating surplus export production capacity, and strengthening trade relationships with the EU.
- **SDG 13: Climate Action:** Adopting Good Agricultural Practices (GAP) in the poultry sector contributes to climate-friendly farming practices. Sustainable

practices reduce the environmental footprint of poultry farming, aligning with global climate goals (UNFCCC, 2015). This compliance with international environmental standards enhances the sector's reputation and competitiveness in the EU market, which increasingly values sustainable products.

- **SDG 15: Life on Land:** Sustainable management of land ecosystems is crucial for the long-term viability of the poultry sector. Moreover, practices that support land conservation and biodiversity help maintain healthy ecosystems. Also, sustainable land management practices ensure that agricultural production does not degrade the environment, which is essential for maintaining access to environmentally conscious markets such as the EU.

Legal Instruments

1. Domestic Legislation

- *Ghana Livestock Development Policy and Strategy (GLDPS) 2016*

The strategy aims to alleviate poverty, improve livestock production and productivity, and ensure environmentally sustainable practices. It provides a comprehensive framework to enhance the poultry sector's productivity and sustainability. Furthermore, it supports small-scale farmers, promotes disease control, and encourages value addition to livestock products.

It includes provisions to support small-scale farmers and focus on improving livestock producers' production, productivity, and income, especially women and small-scale farmers. It also concentrates on disease control, early warning systems, disease prevention, control, and eradication. The policy contains provisions on training and research, as well as supporting training, research, and development initiatives. In connection, it also promotes indigenous breeds' conservation and genetic improvement. The GLDPS aims to increase the availability of feed and fodder resources while also encouraging value-added activities such as processing and packaging. The GLDPS provides a comprehensive framework to enhance the poultry sector's productivity and sustainability. By supporting small-scale farmers and promoting disease control and value addition, the policy helps stabilize local production and market dynamics.

- *Food and Agriculture Sector Development Policy (FASDEP)*

The policy increases food availability and incomes through sustainable agricultural practices. It directly impacts the poultry sector by encouraging diversification and value addition, contributing to improved local production and market stability. The

policy focuses on sustainable practices, encouraging diversification and value addition in agricultural practices. It also provides market support by protecting and promoting the production and consumption of domestic products. The FASDEP directly impacts the poultry sector by promoting sustainable practices and supporting local market development, which helps reduce reliance on imports. The FASDEP generally protects sustainable agricultural practices and supports local markets. This policy is crucial for reducing dependency on poultry imports and boosting local production.

- *Medium-Term Agricultural Development Plan (MTADP)*

The plan aims to modernize agriculture through increased investment, technological advancement, and improved practices. It includes provisions to promote investment in technology, encourage the adoption of modern agricultural technologies, and focus on improving agricultural infrastructure in infrastructure development. The MTADP sets the stage for sector-specific poultry and livestock development interventions, contributing to overall sector growth and competitiveness. The MTADP is cited as foundational in modernizing the agricultural sector through increased investment and technological advancement, which are essential for the growth of the poultry sector.

- *Tax Regimes*

The tax regimes in Ghana are responsible for establishing high import tariffs on poultry to protect local production. Customs duties on poultry inputs such as feed additives and veterinary drugs should be removed to support local production. These tax policies aim to make local production more competitive against imports, encouraging local production and reducing dependency on imported poultry products.

2. European Framework

- *Economic Partnership Agreement (EPA) with the EU*

It provides for a gradual removal of import duties for a significant portion of EU exports to Ghana (see Art.13.2). Poultry meat is excluded from liberalization, maintaining protective tariffs to support local producers. The EPA is highlighted for balancing trade liberalization with the protection of local poultry producers, allowing Ghana to support its domestic industry while engaging in international trade. The exclusion of poultry meat from liberalization under the EPA allows Ghana to maintain protective tariffs, support local producers and ensure market stability.

- *Generalized System of Preferences (GSP) and Everything but Arms (EBA) Initiative*

The GSP and the EBA initiative provide duty-free access to Ghanaian products in the European market. Together, they enhance export opportunities for Ghana's agricultural products, including poultry, thereby boosting trade relations and economic growth. These initiatives are key in enhancing export opportunities for Ghanaian poultry products, contributing to economic growth and trade relations with the EU.

3. International Framework

- *UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and Kyoto Protocol*

They ensure a commitment to reducing greenhouse gas emissions and promoting low-carbon development. Encourages sustainable farming practices in the poultry sector, contributing to environmental sustainability. These agreements commit the signatories to reducing greenhouse gas emissions and promoting low-carbon development. Therefore, it also encourages sustainable farming practices in the poultry sector, contributing to environmental sustainability and resilience to climate change (UNFCCC, 2015). These agreements commit signatories to reducing greenhouse gas emissions and promoting low-carbon development.

- *Multilateral Investment Guarantee Agency (MIGA) and International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID)*

Adherence to MIGA and ICSID Conventions should protect investments against political and non-commercial risks and facilitate the settlement of investment disputes. They should turn Ghana into a secure investment environment, promoting foreign investment in the poultry sector. These agreements protect investments against political and non-commercial risks and facilitate the settlement of investment disputes. These agreements facilitate the development of a secure investment environment and promote foreign investment in the poultry sector.

- *African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA)*

The Act provide preferential access to the US market for Ghanaian products. It expands market access for Ghanaian poultry products, enhancing trade and economic opportunities (see Art. 20). The AGOA is crucial in expanding market access for Ghanaian poultry products and enhancing trade and economic opportunities.

Impact on Trade Between Ghana and the European Union

The legal framework significantly influences trade dynamics between Ghana and the EU. The protective tariffs under the iEPA allow Ghana to shield its poultry sector from intense competition, providing room for local producers to grow. Preferential access to the EU market through initiatives like GSP and EBA boosts Ghana's export potential, helping balance the trade relationship.

The adherence to international standards and protocols, such as ISO certifications and compliance with HACCP, ensures that Ghanaian poultry products meet stringent quality requirements, facilitating smoother trade with the EU. Additionally, international funds (e.g., Green Climate Fund, Adaptation Fund) aid in implementing sustainable practices, enhancing the sector's long-term viability and attractiveness to international buyers.

Unaddressed Areas of Law

- *Intellectual Property Rights (IPR):* The case study does not address intellectual property protection in the poultry sector, such as patents for new breeds or farming technologies.
- *Labour Laws and Workers' Rights:* While there are general references to employment regulations, specific labour laws protecting poultry farm workers' rights, wages, and working conditions are not detailed.
- *Environmental Regulations Specific to Poultry Waste Management:* There is a lack of focus on specific regulations governing poultry waste management and its impact on local ecosystems.
- *Trade and Export Logistics:* Detailed laws or policies governing the logistics of poultry trade and export processes, including transportation, storage, and handling regulations, are not discussed, including transportation, storage, and handling regulations.
- *Consumer Protection Laws:* The framework does not explicitly mention consumer protection laws ensuring the safety and quality of poultry products reaching the market.

Final Remarks

The legal framework encompassing domestic laws, EU regulations, and international agreements plays a crucial role in shaping Ghana's poultry sector. It provides a protective and supportive environment for local production while enhancing trade opportunities with the EU. The alignment with SDGs further strengthens the sector's sustainability and competitiveness. However, gaps in addressing intellectual property rights, specific labour laws, environmental regulations on waste management, detailed trade logistics, and consumer protection laws indicate areas for further development to ensure a comprehensive legal structure supporting the sector's growth and sustainability.

Case Study #6

Analysis of cocoa and chocolate purchasing practices that could undermine living incomes for cocoa farmers (West Africa – Belgium)

Lead organisation & name of lead contact: Oxfam Wereldwinkels, Bart Van Besien

Analysis of the Legal Framework for Cocoa Trade and Production

Introduction

The case study on the Living Income Differential (LID) for cocoa outlines a diverse legal framework that includes domestic, European, and international regulations. These frameworks aim to stabilise cocoa prices, ensure fair income for farmers, and address broader socio-economic and environmental issues. This analysis delves into the specific provisions of each legal instrument mentioned, their impact on cocoa trade and production, and identifies areas of law not addressed in the report.

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Introduction

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) outlined by the United Nations provide a comprehensive framework for promoting sustainable development globally. The case study on the Living Income Differential (LID) for cocoa highlights several SDGs that implicitly influence the cocoa sector. This assessment will explore how these SDGs impact cocoa trade and production activities, particularly between Côte d'Ivoire, Ghana, and the European Union.

- **SDG 1. No Poverty:** Ensuring fair prices for cocoa is essential to improving the livelihoods of cocoa farmers, directly contributing to the eradication of poverty. The LID initiative aims to bridge the income gap for Côte d'Ivoire and Ghana farmers, providing them with a more stable and sufficient income. The initiative can reduce poverty by stabilising farmers' incomes, fostering economic stability in cocoa-producing regions. This stability can lead to a more

reliable cocoa supply for European markets, enhancing trade relations and economic partnerships.

- **SDG 2. Zero Hunger:** Improved income from cocoa farming allows farmers to invest in their food security. With better earnings, farmers can afford to buy food, invest in agricultural inputs, and diversify their crops, leading to better nutrition and food security. Increased food security for farmers ensures that they can sustainably maintain cocoa production levels. This stability benefits European chocolate manufacturers by ensuring a consistent cocoa supply, thus supporting sustainable trade relations.
- **SDG 8. Decent Work and Economic Growth:** The report emphasises the need for better labour rights and living wages in the cocoa sector. Initiatives such as the LID and EU due diligence legislation push for decent work conditions, reducing child labour and exploitation. By promoting decent work, the cocoa sector aligns with the EU's stringent regulations on labour rights, facilitating smoother trade relations. European consumers and regulators demand ethical sourcing, and compliance ensures continued market access.
- **SDG 12. Responsible Consumption and Production:** The call for increased transparency and sustainable business practices is crucial. Regulations on deforestation and sustainability reporting compel companies to adopt responsible production methods. Compliance with EU regulations on sustainability ensures that cocoa from Côte d'Ivoire and Ghana meets the standards required for import. This compliance is essential for maintaining and expanding market access in the EU.
- **SDG 13. Climate Action:** Efforts to combat deforestation and promote sustainable agricultural practices align with climate action goals. Sustainable cocoa farming practices mitigate climate change impacts, preserving ecosystems and reducing carbon footprints. Aligning with EU climate policies facilitates trade by ensuring that cocoa exports meet environmental standards. Sustainable practices enhance the reputation of cocoa from these regions, making it more attractive to European buyers.
- **SDG 15. Life on Land:** The report discusses the importance of combating deforestation and promoting sustainable land use. Protecting forests and biodiversity is crucial for sustainable cocoa production. Meeting EU deforestation regulations ensures that cocoa exports are sustainable. This alignment is crucial for market access, as the EU increasingly prioritises environmental standards in its trade policies.

Legislative Framework

1. Domestic Legislation

- *Ghana's COCOBOD Regulation*

The Ghana Cocoa Board (COCOBOD) plays a crucial role in stabilising cocoa prices and setting farmgate prices to ensure fair income for cocoa farmers. This regulation includes licensing buyers, maintaining a network of buying stations, and using forward sales contracts to secure loans and stabilise prices. The COCOBOD's activities are essential in protecting farmers from price volatility, although challenges remain in ensuring transparency and covering real price losses due to inflation.

COCOBOD requires all cocoa buyers to obtain a license to operate. This regulation ensures that only approved entities participate in cocoa purchasing, aiming to standardise and monitor the trade. COCOBOD mandates the establishment of buying stations to facilitate cocoa collection, ensuring accessibility for farmers. COCOBOD uses forward sales contracts to secure international loans and stabilise cocoa prices, which helps manage financial risks associated with price fluctuations. These provisions aim to stabilise the cocoa market in Ghana, protecting farmers from price volatility and ensuring a steady income. The forward sales contracts, in particular, provide financial security but also impose pressure to sell a significant portion of the harvest in advance, potentially limiting flexibility in response to market changes.

- *Côte d'Ivoire's Conseil du Café-Cacao (CCC)*

Similarly, the Conseil du Café-Cacao (CCC) in Côte d'Ivoire regulates the cocoa market through advance sales mechanisms and stabilisation funds. By facilitating forward sales and setting minimum farmgate prices, the CCC aims to protect farmers from market fluctuations. However, compliance with minimum price payments and the challenges of covering costs for cooperatives and exporters remain issues.

The CCC organises auctions for advance cocoa sales, where exporters indicate their willing prices (see Decree No. 2011-481, 2011). This mechanism helps predict and stabilise prices. A fund is maintained to balance differences between set prices and market prices, compensating exporters when market prices fall below expectations. The CCC sets minimum farmgate prices to ensure farmers receive a fair income regardless of market fluctuations.

The CCC's advance sales mechanism and price stabilisation fund help mitigate the impacts of price volatility on farmers. The CCC aims to protect farmers' incomes by

setting minimum farmgate prices, although enforcement challenges remain, particularly in remote areas.

2. Regional Initiatives

- *Living Income Differential (LID)*

The Living Income Differential (LID) initiative by Côte d'Ivoire and Ghana adds a premium of \$400 per metric tonne to cocoa prices. This initiative aims to improve farmers' income but has faced challenges, such as companies reducing country differentials to offset the LID. The LID represents a significant step towards ensuring a living income for farmers, although its full potential is yet to be realised due to market manipulations (Oxfam-Wereldwinkels, 2023).

An additional \$400 per metric tonne is added to the cocoa price to support farmers by providing a higher income. Companies often offset the LID by reducing country differentials, which has mitigated the intended benefits of the LID. The LID is a significant step towards ensuring a living income for cocoa farmers in Côte d'Ivoire and Ghana. However, its effectiveness has been undermined by market adjustments, highlighting the need for more vigorous enforcement and cooperative agreements among stakeholders to maintain the premium's benefits.

- *Côte d'Ivoire Ghana Cocoa Initiative (CIGCI)*

The Côte d'Ivoire Ghana Cocoa Initiative (CIGCI) is a collaborative effort to align strategies and stabilise cocoa prices through mechanisms like the LID. This initiative underscores the importance of regional cooperation in addressing market power imbalances and ensuring sustainable cocoa production.

The CIGCI aims to align strategies between the two countries to stabilise cocoa prices. The initiative supports mechanisms such as the LID to ensure higher and more stable prices for cocoa. The CIGCI enhances regional cooperation, which is crucial for exerting collective market influence and stabilising prices. This collaboration is vital for addressing the power imbalances in the global cocoa market.

3. European Legislation

- *EU Due Diligence Legislation on Human Rights in Value Chains*

The upcoming EU due diligence legislation mandates companies to maintain transparency in their value chains, focusing on human rights. This legislation will significantly impact the cocoa sector, requiring companies to ensure fair labour practices and transparency, thereby potentially improving conditions for cocoa farmers.

Companies must maintain transparency in their value chains, particularly concerning human rights practices. Firms must identify, prevent, mitigate, and account for human rights impacts throughout their operations and supply chains. This legislation will significantly impact the cocoa sector by enforcing stricter human rights compliance. Companies must ensure fair labour practices, potentially improving cocoa farmers' conditions.

- *EU Legislation on Deforestation*

EU legislation addressing deforestation includes cocoa, among other import products. This law aims to enforce transparent value chains and prevent deforestation, encouraging sustainable agricultural practices in cocoa production areas. Compliance with this legislation will require cocoa-producing countries to adopt environmentally friendly practices.

The legislation includes cocoa among products regulated to prevent deforestation. Companies must demonstrate that their cocoa supply does not contribute to deforestation. Firms must trace the origins of their cocoa and ensure sustainable sourcing practices. The deforestation legislation will compel cocoa producers to adopt sustainable agricultural practices, reducing environmental degradation and promoting biodiversity. This requirement could lead to higher costs for compliance but ultimately foster a more sustainable cocoa industry.

- *Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD)*

The CSRD mandates detailed reporting on corporate sustainability, affecting major cocoa and chocolate companies. These companies must provide more information about their value chains, promoting transparency and accountability in the sector.

Companies must provide comprehensive reports on their sustainability practices, including environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors. The directive requires detailed disclosure of value chain information, promoting accountability. The CSRD

will increase transparency in the cocoa sector, allowing stakeholders to better assess companies' sustainability practices. This directive encourages firms to improve their ESG performance, benefiting cocoa farmers by promoting fair and ethical trade practices.

- *EU Ban on Goods Produced from Forced Labor*

The forthcoming EU regulation banning imports of goods produced with forced labour will significantly impact the cocoa sector, where reports of forced labour are prevalent. This regulation will compel companies to adhere strictly to labour laws and ensure fair labour practices in their supply chains.

The regulation will prohibit the import of goods produced with forced labour, including cocoa. Companies must ensure their supply chains are free from forced labour, with rigorous checks and documentation. This ban will significantly impact the cocoa sector, where forced labour issues are prevalent. Companies must implement strict labour standards and monitoring systems, improving labour conditions and reducing exploitation.

4. International Framework

- *UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights*

The UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights provide a framework for companies to adhere to human rights standards. Various governments, including Germany, are translating these principles into national legislation to enforce corporate accountability in the cocoa sector.

Companies must respect human rights throughout their operations and supply chains. This principle is crucial for ensuring ethical business practices in the cocoa sector (UN Guiding Principles, Principle 13). Governments must protect human rights and ensure corporate compliance through regulation and enforcement (Government Duty (UN Guiding Principles, Principle 1)).

The UN Guiding Principles provide a comprehensive framework for improving human rights standards in the cocoa sector. Implementation at the national level will enforce corporate accountability and promote ethical business practices.

- *International Cocoa Agreements (ICCA)*

The International Cocoa Agreements (ICCA), implemented by the International Cocoa Organization (ICCO), aim to build a sustainable cocoa economy. The seventh cocoa agreement, in effect since 2012, focuses on achieving fair prices for farmers, emphasising the need for a socially, economically, and ecologically sustainable cocoa sector.

The agreements aim to stabilise cocoa prices and ensure fair compensation for farmers. The ICCAs promote economic, social, and environmental sustainability in the cocoa sector.

The ICCAs support a more stable and equitable cocoa market, benefiting farmers by ensuring fair prices and promoting sustainability. These agreements are crucial for long-term sector stability and farmer welfare.

Impact on Trade between Côte d'Ivoire, Ghana, and the EU

The alignment with these SDGs enhances cocoa production's sustainability and ethical standards in Côte d'Ivoire and Ghana. This alignment is crucial for meeting the stringent requirements of the European market, which increasingly values sustainability and ethical practices.

- **Market Access and Trade Relations:** Compliance with EU regulations on human rights, environmental sustainability, and ethical labour practices ensures continued and potentially expanded market access for cocoa from Côte d'Ivoire and Ghana. This compliance builds stronger trade relations and trust with European partners.
- **Economic Stability and Growth:** In addressing poverty, food security, and decent work conditions, the cocoa sector becomes more stable and economically viable. This stability attracts investment and supports economic growth in cocoa-producing countries and the EU.
- **Consumer Trust and Demand:** European consumers are becoming more conscious of their purchases' ethical and environmental impact. Ensuring that cocoa production aligns with SDGs enhances consumer trust and demand for sustainably sourced cocoa products.
- **Long-term Sustainability:** Integrating SDGs into the cocoa sector promotes long-term sustainability, which is essential for the industry's viability. Sustainable practices ensure that cocoa farming can thrive, benefiting producers and consumers.

The legal frameworks discussed have profound implications for trade between Côte d'Ivoire, Ghana, and the European Union. Initiatives like the LID and CIGCI aim to stabilise prices and ensure fair income for farmers, enhancing the sustainability of cocoa production. European regulations on human rights, deforestation, and forced labour will enforce stricter compliance and transparency, compelling companies to adopt sustainable and ethical practices in their supply chains. These frameworks address price volatility, market power imbalances, and human rights abuses, fostering a more equitable and sustainable cocoa industry.

These frameworks collectively strive to address issues like price volatility, market power imbalances, and human rights abuses. However, the effectiveness of these measures depends on robust implementation and cooperation among stakeholders, which are essential for realising these benefits.

Unaddressed Areas of Law

The report does not address particular areas of law that are critical to the cocoa sector, including:

- *Intellectual Property Rights:* There is no mention of intellectual property rights related to cocoa varieties or innovations in farming practices. Protecting IPR could incentivise research and development in sustainable cocoa farming techniques.
- *Comprehensive Labor Laws:* While forced labour is mentioned, the report lacks a detailed discussion on broader labour laws, including worker safety, fair wages, and working conditions beyond forced labour concerns.
- *Trade Policies and Tariffs:* The impact of international trade policies and tariffs on cocoa trade is not discussed. Understanding these policies is essential for assessing their influence on market access and competitiveness.
- *Environmental Regulations:* Beyond deforestation, there is limited discussion on other environmental regulations that impact cocoa farming, such as water use, pesticide regulation, and biodiversity conservation.
- *Technology and Innovation in Agriculture:* The role of technology and innovation in improving cocoa farming practices and yields has not been explored. Legal frameworks promoting technological adoption could enhance productivity and sustainability.

Other areas also not covered extensively in the report are:

- *Gender Equality*: The report does not address gender equality in cocoa farming. Ensuring equal opportunities and fair treatment for women in the cocoa sector is crucial for comprehensive sustainable development.
- *Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions*: Strengthening institutions to enforce regulations and protect farmers' rights is vital. The report could discuss the need for robust legal and institutional frameworks to support sustainable cocoa production.

Final Remarks

The alignment of cocoa production with SDGs significantly impacts trade and production activities between Côte d'Ivoire, Ghana, and the European Union. By promoting fair income, decent work conditions, sustainable practices, and environmental conservation, these frameworks ensure a more stable and ethical cocoa sector. Compliance with EU regulations based on these SDGs enhances market access and trade relations, fostering long-term sustainability and economic growth. Addressing the gaps related to gender equality, innovation, and institutional strength will further bolster the sector's alignment with the SDGs and promote holistic, sustainable development.

The legal frameworks surrounding cocoa production and trade, encompassing domestic, European, and international regulations, aim to address price stability, fair income for farmers, human rights, and environmental sustainability. While significant strides have been made, particularly with initiatives like the LID and upcoming EU legislation, challenges remain in ensuring comprehensive compliance and addressing all relevant areas of law. Future efforts should focus on integrating intellectual property rights, comprehensive labour laws, trade policies, environmental regulations, and technological innovation to create a holistic and sustainable cocoa sector.

Case Study #7

Impacts of EU policies on local dairy value chains in West Africa

Lead organisation & name of lead contact: Oxfam-Solidarité, Fairouz Gazdallah & Marieke Kruis.

[Analysis of the Legal Framework Impacting the Dairy Sector in West Africa](#)

[Assessment of the Sustainable Development Goals](#)

The case study report aligns several proposed measures with specific Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to highlight the broader impact on sustainable development. Here is a detailed analysis of each SDG mentioned, its relevance to the dairy sector activities, and its impact on trade between the analysed West African countries and the European Union (EU).

- **SDG 1. No Poverty:** Developing the local dairy sector is pivotal for poverty reduction in West Africa. The sector can create jobs and generate income by increasing local milk production, especially for rural communities and small-scale farmers. The case study recommends increasing the Common External Tariff (CET) on imported powders and abolishing VAT on fresh milk products. These measures are intended to make local dairy products more competitive, boosting local production and creating economic opportunities for farmers and processors. Implementing protective tariffs and supportive tax policies may reduce the dependency on imported dairy products from the EU, fostering local production and potentially reducing poverty. However, these measures could lead to trade tensions if seen as protectionist, potentially impacting trade relations between West African countries and the EU.
- **SDG 2. Zero Hunger:** The local dairy sector ensures food security and nutritional quality in West Africa. Enhancing the sector can help meet the growing demand for dairy products, improving the availability of nutritious food. By supporting local milk production through protective tariffs and tax incentives, the case study aims to increase the availability of affordable, nutritious dairy products. This approach can help reduce hunger and improve dietary diversity among the population. While protective measures may limit imports from the EU, they encourage local production, contributing to food self-sufficiency. This

shift could reduce the food dependency on imports, enhancing food security in the region.

- **SDG 8. Decent Work and Economic Growth:** The dairy sector has significant potential for creating jobs and fostering economic growth, particularly in rural areas where poverty and unemployment are prevalent. The proposed policies, such as higher CET rates and VAT exemptions, are designed to stimulate local dairy production and processing, creating more employment opportunities. These measures can enhance economic activities and contribute to overall economic growth. Increasing local production could reduce the volume of dairy imports from the EU, impacting trade dynamics. However, economic growth and job creation within the local dairy industry could offset this, which would contribute positively to the regional economy.
- **SDG 10. Reduced Inequalities:** Developing the local dairy sector can help reduce economic inequalities by providing income opportunities for marginalised and rural populations. By promoting policies supporting local dairy production, the case study seeks to distribute economic benefits evenly across society, particularly benefiting small-scale farmers and rural communities. While protective measures may reduce inequalities within West Africa, they could lead to criticisms from international trade partners, such as the EU, for potentially violating trade agreements and WTO commitments.
- **SDG 12. Responsible Consumption and Production:** Encouraging sustainable production practices in the dairy sector is essential for long-term environmental and economic sustainability. The report emphasises the need for responsible production practices, such as reducing reliance on imported palm oil-based dairy substitutes that contribute to deforestation. Promoting local milk production aligns with sustainable consumption and production principles. Shifting towards local production reduces the environmental impact of long-distance transport and supports sustainable practices. However, it may affect trade volumes with the EU, a significant exporter of dairy products to the region.

Legislative Framework

1. Domestic Legislation

- *VAT Policies*

West African countries employ VAT policies that impact the dairy sector. For example, Burkina Faso exempts milk products from VAT, while Senegal exempts unprocessed fresh and liquid milk derived from fresh milk but charges VAT on other dairy products. Nigeria also exempts milk in all its forms but charges VAT on yoghurts.

These VAT exemptions aim to make locally produced dairy products more competitive by lowering their overall cost to consumers. The report recommends extending these exemptions to other products and implementing similar regional policies to support the local dairy sector.

VAT policies in West African countries vary but aim to support local industries through exemptions or reduced rates on essential goods.

- **Burkina Faso**

The VAT rate is 18%, but milk and milk products, including powders, are exempt, while VAT is charged on yoghurts.

- *Value Added Tax Act (2023)*

The act establishes the VAT rate at 18%. In its lists, milk and milk products, including powders, are exempt from VAT, with VAT charged on yoghurts. This exemption aims to support local dairy production by reducing consumer costs.

- **Nigeria**

The VAT rate is set at 7.5%. Milk and milk products are generally exempt, except for certain packaged products. The National Dairy Policy (2021) also aims to phase out imports of fat-filled milk powders by 2025.

- *Value Added Tax Act (2021)*

It sets the VAT rate at 7.5%. It also specifies that milk in all forms is exempt from VAT, except for certain packaged products. The National Dairy Policy aims to phase out imports of fat-filled milk powders by 2025, promoting local milk usage.

➤ Senegal

The VAT rate is 18%, with exemptions for unprocessed fresh and liquid milk derived from fresh milk. Other dairy products and fat-filled milk powders are subject to VAT.

- *Value Added Tax Code (2023)*

The act fixes the VAT rate at 18%. It exempts unprocessed fresh and liquid milk derived from fresh milk from VAT, while other dairy products and fat-filled milk powders are subject to VAT. This policy supports local dairy producers by making their products more competitive.

- *National Dairy Policies*

Specific national policies like Nigeria's National Dairy Policy (2021) focus on reducing dependency on imported dairy products by promoting local production. The policy requires processors to blend imported powders with a certain percentage of local milk, gradually increasing to 50% by 2025. This policy aims to create a stable market for local milk producers and stimulate domestic production.

Nigeria's National Dairy Policy (2021) introduces measures such as a ban on imports of fat-filled milk powders by 2025 and mandates that imported powders be blended with local milk. This policy aims to boost local production and reduce dependency on imports.

2. European Legislation

- *Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)*

The CAP directly subsidises European farmers, significantly reducing their production costs and allowing them to export dairy products at lower prices. These subsidies result in dumping, where products are sold below their actual cost of production, undermining local industries in importing countries.

The case study highlights that CAP subsidies contribute to the competitive disadvantage West African dairy producers face. For instance, French dairy farmers receive up to 80% of their income from CAP subsidies, enabling them to export at lower prices.

➤ *Regulation (EU) No 1307/2013*

The Regulation defines direct payments and eligibility criteria for subsidies. It allows member states to provide additional support to particular sectors, including dairy. CAP subsidies lower production costs, enabling competitive pricing of European dairy exports.

The CAP provides subsidies to European dairy farmers, reducing their production costs and enabling them to export dairy products at competitive prices. These subsidies result in dumping practices, where products are sold below production costs, adversely impacting the West African dairy sector.

○ *Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme*

This EU programme funds research projects that influence policy recommendations and implementations in the agricultural sector. The case study is funded by Horizon 2020, reflecting the EU's commitment to supporting sustainable development through research and innovation.

➤ *Regulation (EU) No 1291/2013*

The regulation details allocating funds for research and innovation, including agricultural projects. The case study, funded by Horizon 2020, illustrates the EU's investment in developing sustainable solutions for global challenges.

The program, which funded the study, underscores the EU's involvement in research and development, impacting policy formulation and implementation in various sectors, including agriculture and trade.

○ *Policies on Palm Oil*

The EU's policies on palm oil, used in fat-filled milk powders, indirectly affect the competitiveness of these products. The lack of stringent bans on palm oil imports means that European dairy products using this cheaper fat substitute can be sold at lower prices in West African markets. This practice harms local dairy sectors and raises environmental concerns due to deforestation linked to palm oil production.

➤ *Regulation (EU) 2018/848*

The Regulation covers organic production and labelling of organic products, indirectly addressing sustainable palm oil production. The Regulation promotes environmentally sustainable practices. The case study criticises the EU for not

effectively banning or reducing palm oil imports, which are used in fat-filled milk powders and contribute to deforestation.

The EU's lack of stringent policies on palm oil imports indirectly supports the competitiveness of fat-filled milk powders, which use palm oil as a substitute for milk fat. This practice contributes to deforestation and environmental degradation.

3. International Framework

- *World Trade Organization (WTO) Commitments*

The WTO framework sets the global rules for trade between nations. The Marrakesh Agreement (1994), establishing the WTO, mandates that member countries adhere to bound tariff rates, which are the maximum tariffs they can impose on imports. These commitments restrict West African countries from significantly increasing tariffs to protect local industries without breaching their WTO obligations. This constraint affects their capacity to protect local industries, including the dairy sector, from competitive international imports, particularly from the European Union (EU), which benefits from the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) subsidies.

The case study notes that increasing the Common External Tariff (CET) on imported dairy products might conflict with these WTO commitments. For instance, scenarios involving quantitative restrictions on imports could violate Article XI of the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT), which prohibits such restrictions except under specific circumstances.

- *Marrakesh Agreement Establishing the WTO (1994)*

This article outlines the bound tariff rates that member countries commit to and cannot exceed. The case study highlights the potential breach of these commitments if West African countries raise their Common External Tariff (CET) rates to protect the local dairy sector. The article also prohibits quantitative restrictions on imports and exports, except under specific circumstances, such as for health protection. The case study mentions that scenarios involving quantitative restrictions on dairy imports could conflict with this article unless justified on public health grounds.

- *Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) and West African Economic and Monetary Union (WAEMU)*

ECOWAS and WAEMU directives aim to harmonise trade policies and VAT legislation across member states. The ECOWAS CET, implemented in 2015, categorises products

into five tariff bands to balance the protection of local industries and consumer interests. For example, bulk milk powders are taxed at 5% and classified under the first tariff band as basic necessities or specific inputs.

The case study suggests revising these classifications to increase protection for the local dairy sector by placing imported dairy products into higher tariff bands. Such reclassification would align with the ECOWAS Regional Offensive for the Promotion of Local Milk Value Chains, aiming to boost local production by adjusting trade policies.

➤ *ECOWAS Common External Tariff (2015)*

It establishes five tariff bands for goods, with dairy products like milk powder in the lowest band at 5%. The case study suggests reclassifying dairy products to higher tariff bands (e.g., 35%) to protect local industries, aligning with the ECOWAS Regional Offensive for the Promotion of Local Milk Value Chains.

➤ *WAEMU Directives on VAT Legislation*

Directive 02/98/CM/UEMOA (1998) and Directive 01/2009/CM/UEMOA (2009) aim to harmonise VAT rates and exemptions within WAEMU member states. They stipulate that unprocessed foodstuffs, including milk, are exempt from VAT. The case study highlights the importance of these directives in providing tax exemptions to support the local dairy industry.

ECOWAS and WAEMU provide regional frameworks for economic integration and trade policy harmonisation. The ECOWAS Common External Tariff (CET), effective in 2015, aims to streamline trade policies across member states. However, its low tariff rates on imported milk powders (5% for bulk powders) do not adequately protect the local dairy industry from the influx of cheaper imported products.

○ *Economic Partnership Agreements (EPAs)*

EPAs between the EU and West African countries like Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire involve commitments to reduce or eliminate tariffs on various imports, including dairy products. The interim EPAs with these countries specify phased liberalisation schedules for dairy imports, which poses challenges for local industries. These agreements exacerbate the challenges local dairy producers face by increasing competition from subsidised European imports.

For instance, the EPA with Ghana mandates the liberalisation of whole milk powder and fat-filled milk powder by 2025-2026, undermining local producers' ability to compete with cheaper, subsidised European imports. This liberalisation process conflicts with efforts to increase CET rates on these imports.

The EPA Details the schedules for tariff reductions and eliminations. The case study discusses how these agreements mandate the liberalisation of dairy imports, including whole milk powder and fat-filled milk powder, which undermines local production efforts. It also emphasises the need for cooperation to support local industries. The case study calls for the EU to facilitate acceptance of increased CET rates at both WTO and EPA levels to protect the local dairy sector.

Impact on Trade Between West Africa and the European Union

- *Trade Balance:* The legal frameworks, such as the CAP and EPAs, create trade imbalances by enabling subsidised European dairy products to dominate West African markets. These imports undermine local production, affecting West African countries' trade balance and economic stability. The influx of subsidised European dairy products undermines local production, leading to a trade imbalance. West African countries become more dependent on imports, affecting their foreign exchange reserves and economic stability. The legal frameworks in place create a significant trade imbalance. Subsidised European dairy products flood West African markets, making it challenging for local producers to compete. This dependence on imports affects West African countries' trade balance and economic stability.
- *Market Competition:* Protective measures, like increasing CET rates and VAT exemptions for local dairy products, aim to enhance local competitiveness. These measures could reduce EU dairy imports but may lead to trade disputes if perceived as protectionist, impacting trade relations. Subsidised European imports, particularly fat-filled milk powders, are cheaper and more accessible, making it difficult for local producers to compete. This competition limits the growth of the local dairy sector and reduces the incomes of local farmers and processors. The competitive edge European imports hold due to subsidies and favourable trade agreements (e.g., EPAs) diminishes the viability of local dairy production. The report's simulations of policy changes, such as increasing the CET and abolishing VAT on local milk products, show potential improvements in local competitiveness and market share.
- *Policy Recommendations:* The report recommends increasing CET on imported powders, abolishing VAT on fresh milk products, and banning imports of fat-

filled milk powders or making them conditional on the use of local milk. These policies support local dairy production but require careful balancing with international trade commitments. To mitigate these impacts, the report recommends several measures:

- Increasing the CET on imported powders and making it more flexible to protect local producers. This would protect local producers by making imported products less price-competitive.
- Abolishing VAT on fresh milk products to enhance competitiveness. This would lower the cost of locally produced dairy products, making them more affordable for consumers and competitive against imports.
- Banning the import of fat-filled milk powders or making their import conditional on using local milk. This would ensure a market for local milk producers and support domestic industry growth.

Unaddressed Areas of Law

- *Environmental Law:* The report mentions the environmental impact of dairy farming and palm oil production but does not profoundly explore related legal frameworks, such as those addressing sustainable agricultural practices and deforestation. The environmental impact of dairy farming and palm oil production, including regulations on sustainable practices and deforestation, are mentioned but not deeply explored.
- *Labour Law:* Workers' working conditions and rights in the local dairy sector are not discussed. This includes fair wages, safe working conditions, and labour rights, which are critical for sustainable development.
- *Intellectual Property Law:* The role of intellectual property rights in protecting local dairy brands and traditional knowledge is not considered. This protection ensures local producers benefit from their products and innovations.
- *Consumer Protection Law:* The report does not address legal frameworks ensuring consumer rights and food safety standards in the dairy sector. These laws protect consumers and maintain trust in local dairy products.

Final Remarks

A complex interplay of international, regional, and domestic laws shapes the legal framework impacting the dairy sector in West Africa. WTO commitments, ECOWAS and WAEMU directives, EPAs, and national policies shape a complex environment that impacts local production, trade dynamics, market competitiveness, trade dynamics, and local industry viability. Addressing these challenges requires coordinated efforts, supportive trade and tax policies, and comprehensive legal frameworks covering environmental, labour, intellectual property, and consumer protection laws. Aligning these policies with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) requires coordinated efforts, supportive trade and tax policies, and comprehensive legal frameworks covering environmental, labour, intellectual property, and consumer protection laws.

Case Study #8

Belgian Consumption of Sugarcane Ethanol from Brazil and Peru. Shared responsibilities of human rights violations

Lead organization & name of lead contact: Oxfam Belgium, Alba Saray Pérez Terán

Analysis of the Legal Framework within the Case Study Report

Introduction

The case study examines the Belgian consumption of sugarcane ethanol from Brazil and Peru, focusing on the associated human rights violations and environmental impacts. It highlights the legal instruments and policies that shape the trade and use of biofuels within the European Union, Belgium, Brazil, and Peru. The study emphasizes the need for stringent human rights and environmental due diligence in the biofuels sector, particularly concerning first-generation biofuels like sugarcane ethanol.

Overview of the SDGs in the Context of the Case Study

The case study on the Belgian consumption of sugarcane ethanol from Brazil and Peru is within the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) framework. The SDGs are 17 interconnected global goals designed to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all by 2030. The report highlights several SDGs directly impacted by sugarcane ethanol production and trade, focusing on sustainability's social, environmental, and economic dimensions.

- **SDG 1. No Poverty:** Sugarcane ethanol production significantly impacts poverty levels in producing regions. While the biofuel industry can create jobs, the case study reveals that these jobs are often low-paying and associated with poor working conditions, particularly for women and indigenous communities. The displacement of local communities and acquiring land at below-market prices exacerbate poverty.

- **SDG 2. Zero Hunger:** The increasing demand for sugarcane ethanol directly impacts food security. Land and resources that could be used for food production are diverted to biofuel crops, leading to higher food prices and reduced food availability. This is particularly critical in regions where food insecurity is a significant issue.
- **SDG 5. Gender Equality:** The report highlights gender-specific impacts of sugarcane ethanol production. Women, especially those related to sugarcane workers, face increased workloads due to their partners' long hours and inadequate wages. Additionally, women often bear the brunt of water contamination and other environmental impacts, which increase their unpaid care and domestic work.
- **SDG 8. Decent Work and Economic Growth:** While biofuel production can contribute to economic growth, the quality of employment in the sugarcane ethanol sector is often poor. Workers face labour rights violations, including discrimination, inadequate wages, and unsafe working conditions. This SDG promotes sustained, inclusive, sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment, and decent work.
- **SDG 10. Reduced Inequality:** The report underscores how the benefits of the biofuel industry are unevenly distributed, often exacerbating existing inequalities. Large agribusinesses and investors profit substantially, while local communities and workers bear the negative social and environmental costs. Addressing these inequalities is crucial for sustainable development.
- **SDG 12. Responsible Consumption and Production:** The sustainability of biofuels, including sugarcane ethanol, is contentious. The case study calls for the EU to phase out land-based biofuels and only allow advanced biofuels after thorough human rights and environmental impact assessments. This SDG emphasizes the need for sustainable consumption and production patterns, a critical issue in the biofuel sector.
- **SDG 13. Climate Action:** The EU's Renewable Energy Directive aims to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by promoting renewable energy sources like bioethanol. However, the environmental impacts of sugarcane ethanol production, including deforestation and water pollution, can undermine these climate goals. Effective climate action requires a comprehensive assessment of all environmental impacts.
- **SDG 15. Life on Land:** The expansion of sugarcane plantations for ethanol production leads to deforestation, loss of biodiversity, and land degradation.

Protecting terrestrial ecosystems and promoting sustainable land use are critical components of this SDG. The report highlights the need for better enforcement of environmental protections in biofuel policies.

- ***SDG 16. Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions:*** The case study documents human rights violations linked to sugarcane ethanol production, including labour abuses and land dispossession. Strengthening institutions and ensuring justice for affected communities are essential for achieving this SDG. This involves improving transparency, accountability, and enforcement of human rights standards in the biofuel supply chain.

Legislative Framework

1. Domestic Legislation

Belgian Legislation

- *Federal Law on Biofuel Incorporation (2009)*

This law mandates the incorporation of biofuels in fossil fuels, which has driven the increased use of bioethanol in Belgium. Despite the law's intention to promote sustainability, the study shows significant negative impacts on producing countries. This law mandates that all registered fossil fuel companies in Belgium incorporate at least 8.5% bioethanol into their fuel mix. The law establishes penalties for non-compliance and sets a framework for monitoring and reporting the biofuel content and its sustainability. This legislation has been crucial in driving the demand for bioethanol in Belgium.

- *Royal Decree of 2018*

This decree set ambitious targets for biofuel incorporation in transport fuels, further incentivizing the import of bioethanol from countries like Brazil and Peru. This decree increased the biofuel incorporation target to 8.5% by 2020, with a cap of 7% for first-generation biofuels like sugarcane ethanol. This policy aims to ensure compliance with the EU's Renewable Energy Directive (RED) targets while promoting the use of advanced biofuels.

2. European Legislation

Renewable Energy Directive (RED II and RED III)

- *RED II (Directive 2018/2001/EU)*

This directive sets a framework for using renewable energy within the EU. It limits the share of biofuels produced from food and feed crops to address sustainability concerns and mandates a gradual phase-out of high ILUC-risk (Indirect Land Use Change) feedstocks like palm oil by 2030. Red II sets the overall EU target for the share of renewable energy in gross final energy consumption at 32% by 2030 and a specific target for renewable energy in transport, mandating that at least 14% of the energy consumed in road and rail transport in each Member State must come from renewable sources by 2030. The directive also requires Member States to submit biannual reports on their biofuel policies' environmental and social impacts, including deforestation and human rights violations in third countries.

The report discusses how RED II drives the production of sugarcane-based bioethanol, leading to environmental and social impacts in Brazil and Peru. The directive's sustainability criteria are highlighted as insufficient to prevent these negative impacts.

- *RED III (Directive (EU) 2023/2139)*

It came into force in 2023, introducing new targets while maintaining the cap on food and feed crop biofuels at 7%. The latest iteration of the Renewable Energy Directive, RED III, introduces more ambitious targets, aiming for a 42.5% share of renewable energy by 2030. The RED III updates the sustainability criteria and introduces stricter measures for transparency and monitoring of biofuels supply chains. It maintains the cap on food and feed crop biofuels at 7% and introduces a combined sub-target for renewable fuels from non-biological origins and advanced biofuels. RED III also emphasizes the need for robust sustainability criteria and improved transparency in biofuel supply chains.

The report calls for the EU to entirely phase out land-based biofuels in the RED targets by 2025 and emphasizes the need for advanced biofuels to undergo robust human rights and environmental impact assessments.

- *Regulation on the Governance of the Energy Union and Climate Action (EU) 2018/1999*

This Regulation ensures coherence in implementing the EU's Energy Union Strategy and aligns it with the Paris Agreement on climate change. According to it, member states must develop and submit integrated national energy and climate plans (NECPs) every ten years, including those affecting third countries. The Regulation mandates the establishment of a public platform to ensure transparency and public participation in energy and climate policies. The report uses this Regulation to highlight the gaps in reporting and transparency, particularly concerning the social impacts of biofuel production in third countries.

- *Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive – CSDDD*

The report discusses specific aspects of the CSDDD concerning bioethanol. It notes that the CSDDD obligates companies to identify actual and potential adverse human rights and environmental impacts arising from their operations and value chains. Moreover, it would require companies to establish and maintain a due diligence policy. The directive outlines the measures companies must take to prevent and mitigate adverse impacts. It mandates that companies provide remediation for adverse impacts they have caused or to which they contributed. The report emphasizes the importance of the CSDDD in ensuring that companies involved in the sugarcane ethanol supply chain conduct thorough due diligence to prevent human rights abuses and environmental damage.

- *Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive – CSRD (Directive 2022/2464/EU)*

The directive expands the scope of non-financial reporting to include detailed disclosures on environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors. It requires companies to report their sustainability risks, opportunities, and impacts, including those related to their supply chains. The report calls for enhanced transparency and accountability through the CSRD, particularly for bioethanol production and trade companies.

This directive expands the scope of reporting requirements to include all large companies and listed SMEs. It mandates detailed disclosures on sustainability matters, such as environmental rights, social rights, human rights, and governance factors. The CSRD aims to enhance transparency and accountability regarding

companies' impacts on people and the planet, reinforcing the objectives of the CSDDD.

3. International Framework

o International Labour Organization (ILO) Conventions

The EU's Trade and Sustainable Development (TSD) chapters in trade agreements require adherence to international labour standards, including the ratification of ILO conventions. This is crucial for ensuring fair labour practices in the bioethanol supply chain. This is crucial for ensuring fair labour practices in the bioethanol supply chain and addressing child and forced labour issues. In particular, the report references:

- *Convention No. 87: Freedom of Association and Protection of the Right to Organise.*
- *Convention No. 98: Right to Organise and Collective Bargaining.*
- *Convention No. 182: Worst Forms of Child Labour.*

The report stresses the need for adherence to ILO conventions to address labour rights violations in the sugarcane ethanol sector in Brazil and Peru.

o United Nations Working Group on Business and Human Rights

The report references assessments by this group regarding the EU's draft due diligence directive, emphasizing the need for robust human rights protections in corporate operations. The UN Working Group advocates for comprehensive human rights due diligence across all sectors, including biofuels. In particular, the report notes:

- *Pillar 1: The state's duty to protect human rights.*
- *Pillar 2: The corporate responsibility to respect human rights.*
- *Pillar 3: Access to remedy for victims of business-related abuses.*

The report references the UNGPs to advocate for more robust human rights, due diligence and accountability mechanisms in the bioethanol supply chain.

o EU-Mercosur Trade Agreement

This Agreement aims to promote trade between the EU and Mercosur countries, including Brazil. It faces concerns regarding its potential climate and deforestation impacts, which are significant given Brazil's role in supplying sugarcane ethanol. The

European Commission has sought commitments from Mercosur countries to address these environmental concerns before ratification.

The Agreement would commit the parties to promote sustainable development through trade-related policies and practices. It would require adherence to multilateral environmental agreements and the effective implementation of international labour standards. The report highlights the potential environmental and social impacts of the EU-Mercosur Trade Agreement, particularly concerning the deforestation and labour rights issues in Brazil's sugarcane sector.

Analysis of Trade Impact between Countries and the EU

The legal framework governing bioethanol trade between Belgium, Brazil, and Peru significantly impacts the activities studied in the case report. The EU's policies, particularly the RED II and RED III directives, drive the demand for bioethanol as part of the EU's renewable energy targets. This demand incentivizes sugarcane ethanol production in Brazil and Peru, often at the expense of environmental and social standards.

- *Trade Dynamics and Economic Impact:* The increase in bioethanol consumption in Belgium, driven by EU and Belgian policies, has led to more significant imports from Brazil and Peru. This trade dynamic has resulted in significant social and environmental impacts in the producing countries, including human rights violations and environmental degradation. The demand for sugarcane ethanol in the EU, driven by policies like the RED II and RED III directives, has significant economic implications for Brazil and Peru. These countries have increased their bioethanol production to meet EU demand, impacting local economies and trade balances. However, the economic benefits are often concentrated among large agribusinesses and investors, while local communities face negative social and environmental impacts.
- *Transparency and Accountability:* The lack of transparency in the bioethanol supply chain hampers efforts to hold companies accountable for the negative impacts of their operations. EU legislation, such as the CSDD and CSRD, aims to address these issues by requiring greater transparency and due diligence in corporate supply chains. The EU's regulatory framework, including the RED II and RED III directives, shapes the trade dynamics by setting sustainability criteria and targets for biofuel use. These policies influence the flow of bioethanol from Brazil and Peru to the EU, creating economic opportunities and environmental and social challenges. Enhanced due diligence and sustainability

reporting requirements under the CSDDD and CSRD aim to address these challenges by promoting more responsible trade practices.

- *Sustainability Criteria and Human Rights:* The EU's Renewable Energy Directives set sustainability criteria for biofuels, but the enforcement and effectiveness of these criteria are questioned. The study suggests that current policies do not adequately prevent the adverse impacts associated with bioethanol production, calling for stricter regulations and better monitoring mechanisms. The alignment of trade policies with the SDGs is critical for ensuring that the economic benefits of bioethanol trade do not come at the expense of human rights and environmental sustainability. The report calls for stricter enforcement of sustainability criteria, improved transparency in supply chains, and robust human rights due diligence to mitigate the negative impacts of bioethanol production.

Unaddressed Areas of Law

- *Comprehensive Coverage:* While the EU has implemented several directives to promote sustainability and human rights, there are gaps in their coverage. For instance, the CSDDD applies primarily to large companies, potentially excluding smaller companies that are significant players in the bioethanol supply chain.
- *Sector-Specific Regulations:* The case study indicates a need for more sector-specific regulations that address the unique challenges of the bioethanol industry. Current policies may not fully capture bioethanol production, trade complexities, and specific risks.
- *Enforcement and Implementation:* Effective enforcement of existing laws and regulations remains challenging. The case study highlights issues with implementing sustainability criteria and the lack of robust monitoring and reporting mechanisms.

Final Remarks

Integrating the SDGs into the legal and policy frameworks governing bioethanol trade between the EU, Brazil, and Peru is essential for promoting sustainable development. The legal framework within which the case study operates comprises a mix of domestic, European, and international laws aimed at promoting sustainable development, human rights, and environmental protection. While these laws significantly impact the activities studied in the report, notable gaps and challenges

exist in their enforcement and coverage. Addressing these gaps through stricter regulations, better enforcement mechanisms, and increased transparency will mitigate the negative impacts of bioethanol production and trade between Belgium, Brazil, Peru, and the European Union.

Case Study #9

Human right due diligence in the coffee value chain

Lead organisation & name of lead contact: Oxfam Wereldwinkels, Sarah Vaes

Contributions by [C-Lever](#)

Analysis of the Legal Framework Impacting the Coffee Value Chain in Uganda

Introduction

The coffee value chain in Uganda, particularly the case study focusing on the Ankole Coffee Producers Cooperative Union (ACPCU), operates within a complex legal framework encompassing domestic, European, and international laws. This analysis will assess how these laws impact the activities studied in the report, influence trade between Uganda and the European Union, and highlight areas of law not addressed in the report.

Assessment of the SDGs in the Report and Their Impact

The coffee value chain in Uganda, particularly the ACPCU, operates within the framework of various Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This assessment will analyse how these SDGs impact the activities studied in the report, influence trade between Uganda and the European Union, and affect overall sustainability and development.

- **SDG 2. Zero Hunger:** SDG 2 aims to end hunger, achieve food security, improve nutrition, and promote sustainable agriculture. Relevant targets include doubling small-scale food producers' agricultural productivity and incomes and ensuring sustainable food production systems. Promoting sustainable agricultural practices within the coffee value chain aligns with SDG 2. Improved productivity and income for coffee farmers in Uganda contribute to food security and poverty reduction. Enhancing the quality and sustainability of coffee production can make Ugandan coffee more competitive in the EU market, aligning with EU preferences for sustainably sourced products.
- **SDG 8. Decent Work and Economic Growth:** SDG 8 promotes sustained, inclusive, and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment, and decent work for all. It emphasises improving labour conditions, increasing

economic productivity, and eradicating forced labour. Implementing fair labour practices and improved working conditions in the coffee value chain supports SDG 8. Compliance with labour laws, such as the Employment Act and ILO conventions, enhances worker safety and rights. Adhering to decent work standards can boost the reputation of Ugandan coffee in the EU market, which increasingly values ethical sourcing and fair labour practices.

- **SDG 12. Responsible Consumption and Production:** SDG 12 aims to ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns. It includes targets such as reducing waste generation, encouraging sustainable practices, and integrating sustainability information into reporting cycles. Adopting sustainable farming practices, waste management and compliance with environmental regulations within the coffee value chain align with SDG 12. The report highlights the need for improved waste management and reduced environmental impact in coffee production. Compliance with SDG 12 can enhance the marketability of Ugandan coffee in the EU, where consumers are increasingly concerned with sustainability and ethical production.
- **SDG 13. Climate Action:** SDG 13 calls for urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts by integrating climate measures into national policies, strategies, and planning. The report discusses aligning coffee production practices with climate action goals, including reducing greenhouse gas emissions and promoting climate-resilient agricultural practices. Aligning with SDG 13 can improve the environmental sustainability of Ugandan coffee, making it more attractive to EU markets committed to reducing their carbon footprint.
- **SDG 15. Life on Land:** SDG 15 aims to protect, restore, and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, manage forests sustainably, combat desertification, and halt biodiversity loss: sustainable land use and conservation practices in coffee farming support SDG 15. The Environmental Management and Coordination Act helps address deforestation, soil erosion, and biodiversity conservation. Compliance with environmental standards enhances the sustainability credentials of Ugandan coffee, appealing to environmentally conscious EU consumers.
- **SDG 17. Partnerships for the Goals:** SDG 17 emphasises the need for strong global partnerships to support sustainable development, focusing on finance, technology, capacity-building, and trade. Collaboration between Ugandan coffee producers, international organisations, and the EU supports capacity-building and sustainable practices in the coffee value chain. Strong partnerships facilitate access to international markets, improve trade relations, and enhance the capacity of Ugandan producers to meet EU standards.

Legislative Framework

1. Domestic Laws

- *Uganda's National Coffee Act*

The National Coffee Act (2021) regulates the coffee industry in Uganda, including registering coffee farmers, quality control measures, and promoting coffee production and marketing. The Act mandates that all coffee farmers, processors, and exporters be registered, ensuring traceability and quality control throughout the value chain. By mandating registration and quality control, the Act aims to improve the competitiveness of Ugandan coffee in the global market, aligning with international trade requirements and enhancing sustainability practices. It is crucial for supporting the sustainable development of the coffee sector by providing a structured approach to coffee farming, processing, and exportation.

The report highlights the importance of this Act for maintaining quality standards and ensuring that coffee from Uganda meets international trade requirements, thereby enhancing its marketability and sustainability.

- *Environmental Management and Coordination Act*

This Act governs environmental protection and management in Uganda. The Environmental Management and Coordination Act provides guidelines for sustainable land use, conservation of natural resources, and prevention of environmental degradation. Key provisions include the requirement for environmental impact assessments (EIA) for significant projects and strict regulations on waste management and pollution control. This Act is crucial for addressing environmental challenges such as deforestation, soil erosion, and water pollution in the coffee value chain, ensuring that coffee production practices are sustainable and environmentally friendly.

Amongst other things, there is a requirement for Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs) for significant projects and regulations on waste management and pollution control. From the report, it can be drawn that there is a need for strict enforcement of these provisions to address environmental challenges in coffee production, such as deforestation, soil erosion, and water pollution. These measures are crucial for sustainable agriculture and compliance with international environmental standards.

- *Employment Act*

The Employment Act outlines the rights and responsibilities of employers and employees, including working conditions, employment contracts, wages, and protection against discrimination and harassment. It also mandates regular payment of wages and sets the minimum wage. This Act is essential for ensuring fair labour practices in the coffee value chain, helping to address issues such as working hours, minimum wage, and workplace safety. It protects workers' rights and promotes decent working conditions.

Amongst the many rights, the Act protects workers' rights, including fair wages and non-discrimination, as well as requirements for employment contracts and working conditions. The report emphasises the role of the Employment Act in promoting fair labour practices within the coffee value chain, ensuring decent working conditions and compliance with international labour standards.

- *Occupational Safety and Health Act*

This Act sets workplace safety and health standards, requiring employers to provide safe working conditions, appropriate equipment, and training to prevent workplace accidents and occupational diseases. Ensuring safe working conditions is vital in the coffee industry to reduce workplace hazards and promote the well-being of workers, enhancing overall productivity and sustainability.

- *Land Act*

The Land Act governs land ownership, use, and management, including regulations on land tenure systems, land transactions, and dispute resolution mechanisms. It provides for the recognition of customary land rights and aims to streamline land registration processes. Proper land use management is critical for sustainable agricultural practices. This Act helps address land ownership issues, ensuring coffee farmers have secure land tenure and can invest in long-term sustainability practices.

The Act sets out land tenure systems and registration processes and establishes dispute resolution mechanisms for land ownership issues. The report points out that secure land tenure and proper land management practices are essential for sustainable coffee farming, addressing land ownership issues, and ensuring long-term investments in the coffee sector.

- *Uganda Revenue Authority Act and Uganda Export Promotion Board Act*

These Acts establish the Uganda Revenue Authority (URA) and the Uganda Export Promotion Board (UEPB) to administer tax laws and promote exports. They include regulations on import and export duties, taxation, and trade facilitation. These institutions are crucial for ensuring that coffee producers and exporters meet their legal obligations and can access international markets, enhancing the export potential of the coffee industry.

These acts establish the mandate of the Uganda Revenue Authority to administer and enforce tax laws. They also outline the role of the Uganda Export Promotion Board in promoting exports and facilitating market access. The report underscores the importance of these acts in supporting coffee exporters by ensuring compliance with tax regulations and providing market information and support, enhancing the competitiveness of Ugandan coffee in international markets.

2. European Framework

- *Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD)*

The Directive expands reporting requirements to include all large companies and listed SMEs, mandating detailed reporting on sustainability issues, including environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors. It enhances transparency and accountability regarding companies' impacts on people and the planet, promoting sustainable business practices and strengthening corporate responsibility. This aligns with Uganda's coffee value chain's goals to adhere to high sustainability standards (European Commission, 2021).

The Directive requires companies to disclose information on their sustainability targets, and due diligence processes and mandates reporting on environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors. The report discusses how these provisions enhance transparency and accountability, ensuring that Ugandan coffee exporters meet EU sustainability and corporate responsibility standards, which is crucial for market access.

- *Renewable Energy Directive II (RED II) and Renewable Energy Directive III (RED III)*

RED II and RED III address the sustainability of biofuel production, limiting the share of biofuels from food and feed crops and setting environmental criteria related to

deforestation, greenhouse gas emissions, and biodiversity. RED III raises the renewable energy target to 45% by 2030. These directives promote the use of sustainable energy sources and address socio-environmental concerns, ensuring that biofuel production does not negatively impact food security or environmental sustainability. This has implications for coffee production practices that may intersect with biofuel production.

They set renewable energy targets for member states, limit the share of biofuels from food and feed crops, and include sustainability criteria. Furthermore, they increase the renewable energy target to 45% by 2030. The report highlights the impact of these directives on promoting sustainable energy sources and addressing socio-environmental concerns, which can influence sustainable practices in coffee production, particularly concerning biofuel production.

- *Regulation on the Governance of the Energy Union and Climate Action*

This regulation ensures coherent implementation of the EU's Energy Union Strategy, aligning it with the Paris Agreement. It covers areas such as energy security, market integration, energy efficiency, decarbonisation, and research and innovation. By promoting a sustainable energy framework, this regulation supports efforts to reduce the environmental impact of coffee production, contributing to broader sustainability goals. The report indicates that aligning coffee production practices with these regulations supports efforts to reduce environmental impact, contributing to broader sustainability goals and compliance with EU regulations.

- *Proposed Import Ban on Goods Produced Using Forced Labour*

This proposed legislative instrument aims to ban products made with forced labour from entering the EU market, establish effective traceability mechanisms, and enforce human rights standards in trade. Strengthening human rights protections in trade ensures that products entering the EU market, including coffee, adhere to ethical labour practices, promoting fair labour conditions in the coffee value chain.

The proposed instrument would establish mechanisms for banning products made with forced labour from entering the EU market. It would also mandate traceability and enforcement mechanisms to ensure compliance. The case study report emphasises the importance of these provisions in eventually promoting ethical labour practices and preventing the importation of goods produced with forced labour, ensuring that Ugandan coffee complies with EU human rights standards.

- *Trade and Sustainable Development (TSD) Policy*

TSD chapters in EU trade agreements require adherence to international labour and environmental standards, preventing trade practices from undermining these standards. The European Commission has proposed action points to enhance the effectiveness and enforcement of TSD chapters. By promoting sustainable trade practices, these policies ensure that trade activities align with sustainable development goals, supporting ethical and sustainable practices in the coffee value chain.

The report discusses how these policies prevent trade practices that undermine sustainability standards and promote ethical trade practices, enhancing the reputation and marketability of Ugandan coffee in the EU.

3. International Framework

- *International Labour Organization (ILO) Conventions*

ILO Conventions promote fair labour practices and ensure decent work conditions, with specific conventions related to child labour (Convention No. 138 and No. 182) and forced labour (Convention No. 29 and No. 105). Compliance with these conventions is essential for maintaining ethical labour practices in the coffee industry, which guides corporate and governmental policies to eliminate exploitative labour practices. More specifically, the following conventions are mentioned:

- *Convention No. 138:* Minimum Age Convention, setting the minimum age for employment.
- *Convention No. 182:* Worst Forms of Child Labour Convention, aiming to eliminate child labour.
- *Convention No. 29:* Forced Labour Convention, prohibiting forced or compulsory labour.
- *Convention No. 105:* Abolition of Forced Labour Convention.

The report highlights these conventions as essential for promoting fair labour practices and ensuring decent work conditions in the coffee value chain, guiding policies to eliminate exploitative labour practices.

- **Paris Agreement**

The Paris Agreement is a crucial international framework for combating climate change, aligning with EU legislation to reduce environmental impacts. Adhering to the Paris Agreement's targets is essential for mitigating greenhouse gas emissions and promoting sustainable agricultural practices in the coffee value chain.

In particular, the Agreement aims to limit global warming to below 2 degrees Celsius. It also mandates nationally determined contributions (NDCs) to reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

The report discusses the alignment of coffee production practices with the Paris Agreement, emphasising the need to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and promote sustainable agricultural practices to mitigate climate change impacts.

Impact on Trade Between Uganda and the EU

The alignment with the SDGs and compliance with the specific legal provisions discussed have significant implications for trade between Uganda and the European Union:

- *Enhanced Market Access:* Compliance with the CSRD, TSD policy, and other EU directives ensures that Ugandan coffee meets the stringent sustainability and ethical standards required by the EU market, facilitating market access. Adherence to SDGs such as decent work, responsible production, and climate action can enhance Uganda's market access to the EU, prioritising sustainable and ethically produced goods.
- *Increased Competitiveness:* Adopting sustainable and ethical practices as mandated by the various legal instruments improves the competitiveness of Ugandan coffee, appealing to the EU's sustainability-conscious consumers.
- *Support for Sustainable Development:* Alignment with the SDGs supports overall sustainable development in Uganda, contributing to economic growth, improved livelihoods, and environmental conservation, which are attractive for EU trade partners.
- *Compliance with EU Regulations:* Meeting the requirements of EU legislation through SDG-aligned practices ensures smooth trade relations and enhances the reputation of Ugandan coffee in the international market.

The legal frameworks discussed have significant implications for trade between Uganda and the European Union:

- **Enhanced Transparency and Accountability:** The CSRD and other EU directives mandate comprehensive reporting on sustainability and due diligence processes, ensuring that Ugandan coffee exports meet stringent EU standards.
- **Sustainability and Ethical Practices:** Compliance with international agreements such as ILO conventions and the Paris Agreement promotes sustainable and ethical practices in the Ugandan coffee sector, aligning with EU import requirements.
- **Market Access and Competitiveness:** Adherence to domestic laws like the National Coffee Act and environmental regulations enhances the quality and sustainability of Ugandan coffee, improving its competitiveness in the EU market.
- **Trade Facilitation and Support:** The Uganda Export Promotion Board and trade-related regulations support Ugandan coffee exporters accessing international markets, facilitating trade missions, and promoting Ugandan coffee globally.

Unaddressed Areas of Law

The report does not explicitly address particular areas of law that could impact the coffee value chain:

- **Intellectual Property Rights:** The report does not provide enough information on protecting indigenous coffee varieties and branding of Ugandan coffee.
- **Digital Trade and E-commerce:** The report does not address Legal frameworks governing the digitalisation of trade and the use of technology in the coffee value chain.
- **Climate Change Adaptation:** The case study does not discuss specific laws and policies addressing climate resilience and adaptation strategies for coffee farmers.
- **Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment:** There is limited information on laws promoting gender equality and women's participation in the coffee industry.

Final Remarks

Integrating the SDGs and compliance with specific legal provisions within the Ugandan coffee value chain enhances sustainability, ethical practices, and competitiveness. This alignment supports Uganda's sustainable development goals and strengthens its trade relations with the European Union by ensuring compliance with stringent EU standards for sustainability and ethical sourcing. Continued focus on the SDGs and legal compliance will be crucial for the long-term viability and success of the Ugandan coffee industry in the global market.

A combination of domestic, European, and international laws shapes the legal framework within the Ugandan coffee value chain. These laws collectively enhance the sustainability, ethical practices, and competitiveness of Ugandan coffee in the global market, particularly the EU. However, some areas of law need further attention to ensure a holistic approach to sustainable development and trade in the coffee sector.

Case Study #10

Beef and policy coherence for sustainable development

Lead organization & name of lead contact: CRPA.

Authors: Alberto Menghi, Lorena Giglio, Serena Soffiantini, Stefano Pignedoli, Assuntina Palamara

Analysis of the Legal Framework for Case Study 10: Beef and Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development

Introduction

Case Study 10, titled "Beef and Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development," focuses on the impact of labour conditions and costs on the competitiveness of the beef industry across nine countries: Morocco, Namibia, South Africa, Argentina, Brazil, United States, France, Germany, and Italy. This analysis assesses how various domestic, European, and international laws influence the activities studied in the report and their impact on trade between these countries and the European Union (EU). Furthermore, it identifies areas of law that should be covered in the report.

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) Addressed

Case Study 10, "Beef and Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development," aligns its analysis with several Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by assessing the impact of labour conditions, costs, and environmental sustainability on the beef industry. This assessment explores how these SDGs influence the activities analyzed and their effects on trade between the studied countries (Morocco, Namibia, South Africa, Argentina, Brazil, United States, France, Germany, and Italy) and the European Union (EU).

- **SDG 1. No Poverty:** Labor legislation helps reduce poverty and improve the livelihoods of beef workers and their families. By ensuring fair wages, decent working conditions, and social protections, labour laws directly contribute to poverty reduction. Improved labour conditions increase the cost of production but enhance workers' quality of life. Fair wages and social protections contribute to economic stability for workers, fostering a more sustainable workforce. Countries with strong labour laws and reduced poverty rates can produce

higher-quality beef, meeting the EU's standards for ethical and sustainable products. Enhanced labour conditions may increase production costs, potentially affecting competitiveness in the global market. However, compliance with EU labour standards can lead to better market access.

- **SDG 2. Zero Hunger:** Labour legislation supports sustainable livestock practices, ensuring food safety and quality while addressing issues such as child labour and forced labour in the beef sector. Ensuring fair labour practices promotes sustainable production methods, contributing to food security. Eliminating child and forced labour enhances the industry's reputation and compliance with international standards. Compliance with SDG 2 helps countries meet the EU's strict food safety and labour standards, facilitating smoother trade relations. Sustainable livestock practices reduce the environmental footprint, align with EU sustainability goals, and increase the attractiveness of beef exports.
- **SDG 3. Good Health and Well-being:** Good legislation ensures fair working practices and the welfare of workers, focusing on workplace safety and reducing hazardous work conditions. Improved health and safety standards reduce workplace accidents and illnesses, leading to a more productive workforce. Fair working conditions contribute to the overall well-being of workers, enhancing job satisfaction and retention. Countries with robust health and safety standards are more likely to meet EU requirements, improving their market access. A healthier workforce can maintain higher productivity levels, supporting consistent supply and meeting international demand.
- **SDG 8. Decent Work and Economic Growth:** Labor legislation promotes inclusive and sustainable economic growth, productive employment, and decent work, protecting workers' rights, ensuring fair wages, and promoting equal opportunities. Ensuring decent work conditions increases job satisfaction and productivity, contributing to economic growth. Fair wages and equal opportunities create a more motivated and efficient workforce. Alignment with SDG 8 enhances the reputation of countries' beef industries, making their products more appealing to the EU market. Sustainable economic growth and decent work conditions attract foreign investments, boosting the industry's competitiveness.
- **SDG 6. Clean Water and Sanitation:** Environmental aspects of cattle breeding impact water use and sanitation practices. Sustainable water management is crucial for reducing the environmental footprint of beef production. Implementation of sustainable water use practices ensures the long-term viability of beef production. Improved sanitation practices reduce the risk of water contamination, protecting the environment and public health. Compliance with

water and sanitation standards is critical for gaining access to the EU market, which prioritizes environmental sustainability. Sustainable water management practices enhance the environmental credentials of beef exports, aligning with EU consumer preferences.

- **SDG 13. Climate Action:** Cattle breeding has significant environmental impacts, including greenhouse gas emissions. The study aims to mitigate these impacts through improved practices. Adopting practices to reduce greenhouse gas emissions can lower the carbon footprint of beef production. Investment in climate-smart agriculture enhances the resilience of beef production systems to climate change. Meeting EU climate action standards can enhance market access and consumer trust. Reducing emissions aligns with global climate commitments, positioning countries as leaders in sustainable beef production.
- **SDG 15. Life on Land:** The case study examined the impact of beef production on land use and aimed to find strategies to reduce negative environmental impacts, such as deforestation and biodiversity loss. Sustainable land management practices protect ecosystems and biodiversity, ensuring the long-term sustainability of beef production. Strategies to reduce deforestation and promote reforestation can enhance the environmental sustainability of beef farms. Compliance with EU environmental standards related to land use can improve market access and consumer acceptance. Sustainable land management practices enhance the reputation of beef exports, aligning with EU environmental priorities.

Legislative Framework

1. Domestic Legislation

Each country in the case study has its labour laws that significantly impact the beef industry. Key domestic legislations referenced include:

Germany

- *Arbeitszeitgesetz (ArbZG)*

The Act regulates working hours and rest periods to ensure worker health and safety, including maximum daily and weekly limits, rest periods, and night work. This law aims to protect workers' health and safety by preventing excessive work hours. It limits daily working hours to 8 hours, which is extendable to 10 hours if the average over six months does not exceed 8 hours. It also ensures minimum rest periods of

11 hours between working days. This is decisive for ensuring safe working conditions and preventing worker fatigue, which can impact productivity and health.

- *Bundesurlaubsgesetz (BUrlG)*

The Act ensures minimum annual leave for employees. It guarantees a minimum of 24 working days of annual leave, ensuring employees' well-being through mandatory rest periods. Ensuring workers have sufficient rest periods contributes to overall well-being and productivity in the beef industry.

- *Entgeltfortzahlungsgesetz (EntgFG)*

The Act provides wage continuation during sickness and public holidays. This means employees receive their regular wages during sickness and public holidays, providing income security during periods of illness. Employees are entitled to six weeks of continued remuneration in case of illness. The Act protects workers' income during illness, ensuring financial stability and reducing absenteeism.

- *Teilzeit- und Befristungsgesetz (TzBfG)*

This Act governs part-time and fixed-term employment to protect workers' rights, promoting flexible working arrangements while ensuring non-discriminatory treatment and equal opportunities for part-time employees. Doing so ensures non-discriminatory treatment and equal opportunities for part-time employees. Furthermore, it promotes flexible working arrangements while protecting workers' rights, essential for a diverse and adaptable workforce in the beef sector.

- *Bürgerliche Gesetzbuch (BGB)*

The BGB covers contract formation and termination, ensuring fair treatment and legal protection. This includes provisions on employment contracts, obligations, and termination and offering employees legal protection and fair treatment. More importantly, it regulates the formation, obligations, and termination of employment contracts while providing a legal framework for fair treatment and legal protection of employees, ensuring stable employment relations.

South Africa

- *Basic Conditions of Employment Act nr 75 of 1997*

The Act sets conditions of employment, including working hours, leave entitlements, termination procedures, and remuneration. The Sectoral Determination 13 (Farm Worker Sector) specifically addresses conditions for agricultural workers, ensuring decent work and fair wages. This Act establishes generally minimum employment standards. In this context, it limits maximum working hours to 45 per week and provides for annual leave entitlement of 21 consecutive days. It details sick leave entitlements and ensures decent working conditions, contributing to worker welfare and productivity.

Brazil

- *Consolidação das Leis do Trabalho (CLT)*

This comprehensive labour law code covers working hours, employment conditions, workers' rights, and employer obligations. It includes specific provisions for agricultural workers, addressing issues such as working hours, overtime pay, and health and safety standards. The code limits daily working hours to 8 hours, with a maximum of 44 hours per week and mandates a minimum one-hour break for work periods exceeding six hours. It also sets specific conditions for paid leave and regulates working conditions, promoting fair labour practices and worker safety.

France

- *Convention Collective Nationale Production Agricole/CUMA*

The Collective Agreement governs labour conditions in the agricultural sector, covering aspects such as wages, working conditions, social security benefits, and occupational safety standards. It also governs labour conditions in agriculture. The Agreement limits daily working hours to 10, with weekly hours capped at 48, and guarantees at least five weeks of paid leave annually. It ensures compliance with labour standards, promoting worker welfare and productivity.

Italy

- *Contratto Collettivo Nazionale di Lavoro per gli Operai Agricoli e Florovivaisti*

The Agreement outlines the rights and duties of agricultural workers, covering wages, working conditions, and social security. It defines agricultural workers' and employers' rights and duties, including wage structures, working conditions, social security, and health and safety provisions. Amongst other things, it defines the rights and duties of agricultural workers, specifies working hours and rest periods, and details wage structures and overtime compensation. It aims to ensure fair wages and working conditions, contributing to a stable workforce.

2. European Framework

EU regulations and directives provide a framework that influences agricultural practices, labour laws, and environmental standards in member states and their trade partners:

- *EU Regulation (EU) No 1305/2013 (European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development - EAFRD)*

The European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) supports sustainable rural development by improving the competitiveness of agriculture, ensuring the sustainable management of natural resources, and achieving balanced territorial development. The Regulation defines the objectives of improving the competitiveness of agriculture and ensuring the sustainable management of natural resources. Furthermore, it promotes sustainable practices in beef production, enhancing long-term viability and environmental stewardship.

- *EU Regulation (EU) No 1307/2013 (CAP)*

This Regulation establishes direct payment schemes for farmers to promote food security, sustainable agriculture, and rural development. It includes provisions for greening payments to encourage environmentally friendly practices. It also establishes rules for direct payments to farmers and incentivizes sustainable agricultural practices, aligning with environmental goals and improving market access.

- *EU Directive 2003/87/EC (EU ETS Directive)*

The Directive establishes the EU Emissions Trading System to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. This is a scheme for greenhouse gas emission allowance trading within the EU to reduce emissions cost-effectively. The Directive covers key aspects such as allocating and trading emissions allowances. It defines the scope and application of the emissions trading system and encourages the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions in beef production, aligning with EU climate policies.

- *Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme*

The Programme funds projects that drive sustainable growth, including those related to agricultural sustainability. It provides funding for projects aimed at driving sustainable and inclusive growth, including initiatives focused on agricultural sustainability and innovation. It further supports innovation in sustainable beef production, enhancing competitiveness and compliance with EU standards.

These EU frameworks ensure that agricultural practices across member states align with broader sustainability and environmental goals, promoting a balanced approach to economic growth and environmental protection.

3. International Framework

The report references several international frameworks that underscore the importance of labour standards and environmental sustainability:

- *International Labour Organization (ILO) Conventions*

International Labour Organization Conventions emphasize labour rights, including freedom of association and collective bargaining. They highlight that national compliance with labour rights is based on ILO conventions, mainly focusing on freedom of association and collective bargaining (ILO Convention No. 87 and No. 98).

- *Convention No. 87: Freedom of Association and Protection of the Right to Organize.*
- *Convention No. 98: Right to Organize and Collective Bargaining.*

Attention to these Conventions promotes fair labour practices and worker rights.

- *Global Reporting Initiative (GRI)*

The Initiative provides standards for sustainability reporting. It aligns with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to enhance transparency and accountability in sustainability practices (GRI Standards). The Initiative also encourages comprehensive sustainability reporting, improving the industry's reputation and market access.

- *Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Guidelines*

The IPCC Guidelines are used to estimate CO2 emissions related to beef production. They are used for estimating CO2 emissions from beef cattle breeding and transportation, supporting accurate reporting and mitigation strategies for greenhouse gas emissions in beef production.

Impact on Trade between Countries and the EU

Compliance with domestic legislation, EU legislation and international standards significantly impacts trade dynamics:

- **Market Access and Compliance:** Countries adhering to EU labour and environmental standards gain better market access, as their products meet the EU market's rigorous quality and sustainability criteria. For instance, complying with the EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) allows countries to participate in carbon trading, enhancing their environmental credibility and trade relations.
- **Tariffs and Quotas:** The EU trade policies, including tariffs and quotas, shape beef trade dynamics by balancing market access with protection for local producers. Reduced tariffs and increased export opportunities benefit countries with favourable trade agreements with the EU.
- **Sustainability Standards:** Aligning with sustainability standards, such as those outlined in the EU Green Deal and Farm to Fork Strategy, enhances the competitiveness of beef products from compliant countries. These standards promote reduced environmental impact and sustainable agricultural practices.

Unaddressed Areas of Law

While the report provides a comprehensive analysis of labour legislation and environmental sustainability, a few areas of law are not thoroughly addressed:

- *Intellectual Property Rights:* The report does not discuss intellectual property laws related to agricultural innovations, which are vital for protecting and promoting technological advancements in the beef industry.
- *Animal Welfare Laws:* Although environmental impacts are considered, specific regulations on animal welfare, crucial for ethical practices in beef production, are not detailed.
- *Food Safety Regulations:* While food safety is implicitly linked to sustainable practices, specific national and international food safety laws and their enforcement are not extensively analyzed.
- *Trade Dispute Mechanisms:* The mechanisms for resolving trade disputes between countries and within the EU framework are not covered, which are essential for maintaining fair trade practices.

Final Remarks

The alignment of Case Study 10 with the SDGs provides a comprehensive framework for assessing the impact of labour conditions, environmental sustainability, and trade dynamics in the beef industry. The above SDGs influence various aspects of beef production, from labour rights and working conditions to environmental sustainability and economic growth. By adhering to these goals, the studied countries can enhance their competitiveness, meet EU standards, and contribute to global sustainable development. Integrating these SDGs into national policies and practices improves trade relations with the EU and ensures the beef industry's long-term sustainability and ethical integrity.

The legal framework influencing Case Study 10 encompasses domestic laws, EU regulations, and international agreements that collectively shape labour conditions, environmental sustainability, and trade dynamics in the beef industry. Compliance with these frameworks enhances market access, promotes sustainable practices, and aligns with global development goals. However, gaps in intellectual property rights, animal welfare laws, food safety regulations, and trade dispute mechanisms highlight areas for further analysis to understand better the legal landscape impacting the beef industry.

Case Study #11

Private standards and sustainable trade

Lead organization & name of lead contact: Research Centre on Animal Production, Department of Economics and Engineering, Italy.

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

- **SDG 1. No Poverty:** By improving market access and income for smallholder farmers through certification, the project contributes to poverty reduction. This aligns with the goal of eradicating poverty by increasing farmers' income and improving their living standards. This is achieved by enabling farmers to sell their produce at higher prices in international markets, thus increasing their income and reducing poverty.
- **SDG 2. Zero Hunger:** The project aims to enhance food security by improving agricultural practices and market access. Certification ensures that farmers adopt sustainable farming methods, leading to increased productivity and food availability, which addresses food insecurity. **The** certification ensures that farmers adopt sustainable farming methods, increasing productivity and food availability.
- **SDG 5. Gender Equality:** The report discusses gender issues in agricultural practices and certification, aiming to reduce gender disparities. By promoting women's participation and ensuring equal access to resources, the project supports gender equality and empowers women in agriculture.
- **SDG 8. Decent Work and Economic Growth:** The project promotes decent work and economic growth by focusing on labour conditions and certification. As mandated by certifications, improved labour conditions and fair wages contribute to better working environments and economic stability for workers.
- **SDG 12. Responsible Consumption and Production:** Certification encourages sustainable agricultural practices, contributing to responsible consumption and production. By adopting ecological farming methods, farmers reduce their environmental impact and produce sustainably sourced products. Certification encourages sustainable agricultural practices, contributing to responsible consumption and production.

- **SDG 15. Life on Land:** The report mentions the EU deforestation regulation, linking agricultural practices to forest conservation. By preventing deforestation and promoting sustainable land use, the project helps conserve biodiversity and protect ecosystems.

Legislative Framework

1. Domestic Laws

○ **Kenya's Labor Laws**

These include regulations on minimum wage, working hours, and worker benefits. They protect agricultural workers' rights, improve their welfare and promote decent work conditions.

➤ *Employment Act (2007)*

The Act regulates employment terms, conditions, and worker rights, including minimum wage, working hours, and worker benefits. It prohibits discrimination in employment and requires employers to promote equal opportunity.

➤ *Occupational Safety and Health Act (2007)*

The Act ensures safe working conditions for all workers, including those in agriculture. Generally, the Act mandates that employers ensure the health, safety, and welfare of all persons working on their premises.

These laws protect agricultural workers' rights, promote decent work conditions, and improve overall worker welfare.

○ **Agricultural Policies and Regulations**

These govern crop production, certification processes, and subsidies. They are crucial for ensuring that Kenyan agricultural practices meet domestic and international standards.

➤ *Agriculture and Food Authority (AFA) Act*

This act regulates agricultural practices, standards, and market access and establishes the Agriculture and Food Authority, which applies such regulation to agricultural practices and standards.

➤ *Kenya Plant Health Inspectorate Service (KEPHIS) Act*

The Act regulates the certification and quality of agricultural produce for export. These policies ensure that Kenyan agricultural practices meet domestic and international standards, enhancing the quality and competitiveness of Kenyan produce in global markets.

○ ***Environmental Regulations***

These regulations pertain to sustainable farming practices and environmental conservation efforts, aligning with international environmental goals.

➤ *Environmental Management and Coordination Act (1999)*

This Act provides a framework for environmental management and conservation. It establishes the right to a clean and healthy environment and requires environmental impact assessments for projects likely to have significant environmental effects.

Moreover, it promotes sustainable farming practices and environmental conservation efforts, aligning with international environmental goals.

2. European Framework

○ *EU Deforestation Regulation*

This significant regulation links the certification process and sustainable agricultural practices to forest conservation efforts. The case study's findings on crop uprooting for avocado and mango cultivation highlight the need for compliance with this regulation to prevent deforestation.

This regulation aims to minimize the EU's contribution to deforestation and forest degradation worldwide by ensuring that commodities placed on the EU market do not contribute to deforestation. The report highlights that about 30% of avocado farmers and 25% of mango farmers have uprooted other crops to plant these trees, raising concerns under the EU deforestation regulation. Compliance with this regulation promotes sustainable land use and forest conservation.

- *EU Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme*

The project's funding under this program indicates its alignment with EU research and innovation goals, emphasizing sustainable development and technological advancements in agriculture. This program supports research and innovation projects aimed at sustainable development and technological advancement.

- *General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)*

Mentioned in the context of handling farmer data, GDPR ensures that data collection and usage during the survey process comply with European privacy standards. It guarantees the protection of personal data and privacy of individuals within the EU and the European Economic Area. The mention of GDPR in handling farmer data ensures that the data collection and usage during the survey process comply with stringent European privacy standards, protecting farmers' personal information (European Parliament and Council, 2016). In this context, personal data shall be processed lawfully, fairly, and transparently, with attention given to the lawfulness of processing conditions, including consent.

- *Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)*

Regarding subsidies and support provided to farmers, CAP's framework supports the financial and technical assistance required for sustainable farming practices. It provides subsidies and financial support to farmers within the EU to promote sustainable agriculture. Relevant to the subsidies and support provided to Kenyan farmers, CAP's framework supports the financial and technical assistance required for sustainable farming practices.

3. International Framework

- *International Labour Organization (ILO) Conventions*

ILO conventions focus on labour rights and working conditions. In the context of the case study, they ensure that the labour standards in Kenyan agriculture align with international norms, which helps improve working conditions and promote social sustainability. Two Conventions are referenced in particular:

- *ILO Convention No. 87 (Freedom of Association and Protection of the Right to Organise Convention, 1948)*

This Convention guarantees the rights of workers and employers to form and join organizations of their choosing without prior authorization. These organizations have the right to draw up their constitutions and rules, elect representatives, and organize their administration and activities.

- *ILO Convention No. 98 (Right to Organise and Collective Bargaining Convention, 1949)*

This Convention aims to protect workers against anti-union discrimination and promote collective bargaining. According to the Convention, measures appropriate to national conditions shall be taken to encourage and promote the full development and utilization of machinery for voluntary negotiation between employers or employers' organizations and workers' organizations.

The report emphasizes improving labour conditions and promoting social sustainability. Adherence to these conventions ensures that workers' rights are protected, contributing to better working conditions and fair treatment (ILO, 1948; ILO, 1949).

- United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)

This Convention is crucial for environmental sustainability. The case study's emphasis on sustainable agricultural practices, such as minimizing deforestation and promoting ecological farming, ties directly to the goals of the UNFCCC. The Convention aims to stabilize greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere at a level that would prevent dangerous anthropogenic interference with the climate system.

It aims to stabilize greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere at a level that would prevent dangerous anthropogenic interference with the climate system. In the context of this framework, all parties shall develop and implement measures to mitigate climate change by addressing anthropogenic emissions.

- *Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW)*

In addressing gender equality in agricultural practices, the case study aligns with CEDAW by aiming to reduce gender disparities and promote women's farming participation. In particular, the Convention addresses the rights of rural women,

ensuring their participation in development planning and implementation. The Convention also aims to ensure women's right to work, equal employment opportunities, and social benefits.

The report discusses gender issues in agricultural practices and certification, aiming to reduce gender disparities and promote women's participation in the agricultural sector (CEDAW, 1979).

Impact on Activities and Trade

➤ **Market Access and Trade**

- *Certification and Market Access:* GLOBALG.A.P. certification significantly improves access to international and regional markets, enabling Kenyan farmers to meet the demands of international buyers, particularly in the EU. This aligns with studies highlighting the importance of certification in enhancing market access. Adhering to these standards, Kenyan farmers can produce high-quality, sustainable produce that meets the demands of international buyers, particularly in the EU. The case study notes that certification facilitates access to bank financing and state support, enhancing farmers' financial stability and capacity to invest in better farming practices.
- *EU Deforestation Regulation:* Compliance with this regulation ensures that agricultural practices do not contribute to deforestation, promoting sustainable land use. The report's findings on crop uprooting for avocado and mango cultivation highlight the need for adherence to this regulation. The EU deforestation regulation directly impacts agricultural practices, as farmers need to comply with deforestation-free requirements to access the European market. This regulation encourages sustainable land use and reduces environmental impact.

➤ **Labor and Social Standards**

- *Improved Working Conditions:* Compliance with ILO conventions and Kenya's labour laws ensures better working conditions, fair wages, and the protection of workers' rights, promoting social sustainability and improving the overall welfare of agricultural workers.
- *Gender Equality:* Addressing gender disparities through adherence to CEDAW and related domestic policies enhances gender equality, promoting equitable access to resources and opportunities for women farmers.

➤ **Environmental Sustainability**

- *UNFCCC and EU Environmental Regulations:* The adherence to the UNFCCC and EU environmental regulations ensures that agricultural practices in Kenya are environmentally sustainable. This includes minimizing deforestation, promoting ecological farming practices, and ensuring the long-term sustainability of the agricultural sector.

Impact on Trade Between Kenya and the EU

➤ **Enhanced Market Access**

- *Certification under GLOBALG.A.P.:* It provides Kenyan farmers with the credentials needed to export to the EU, enhancing their market access and enabling them to sell produce at higher prices in the international market. This enhances their market access and allows them to sell their produce at higher prices in the international market.
- *EU Horizon 2020 Funding:* This indicates strong EU-Kenya collaboration, fostering innovation and sustainable practices in Kenyan agriculture and boosting trade relations (European Commission, 2014).

➤ **Regulatory Compliance**

- *EU Regulations:* Compliance with EU regulations such as deforestation and GDPR ensures that Kenyan agricultural exports meet European standards, preventing potential trade barriers and facilitating smoother trade flows.

➤ **Financial and Technical Support**

- *Common Agricultural Policy (CAP):* The CAP provides financial and technical support to Kenyan farmers, enhancing their competitiveness in the EU market (European Commission, 2013).

Unaddressed Areas of Law

- *Intellectual Property Rights:* The report does not discuss the impact of intellectual property rights on agricultural practices, particularly concerning the use of patented seeds and technologies.

- *Consumer Protection Laws:* There is no mention of consumer protection laws related to the safety and quality of agricultural produce, which could be relevant for domestic and international markets.
- *Trade Dispute Resolution:* The report does not cover the mechanisms for resolving trade disputes between Kenyan farmers and international buyers or within the domestic market.

Final Remarks

This analysis provides a comprehensive overview of the legal framework impacting the agricultural practices studied in the case study, highlighting the role of international, European, and domestic laws in shaping sustainable and equitable agricultural trade between Kenya and the EU.

Case Study #12

Ethical Trade Initiatives in the South African Wine Industry

Lead organization & name of lead contact: NWU – Ernst Idsardi

Introduction

Analyzing the legal framework within which the case study on ethical trade initiatives in the South African wine industry is critical for understanding the intersection of various laws and regulations on local, European, and international levels. The report examines specific legal instruments examining their direct impact on the wine industry and trade relations between South Africa and the European Union (EU).

Assessment of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

The case study on ethical trade initiatives in the South African wine industry aligns with several Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), significantly impacting the activities analyzed and trade relations between South Africa and the European Union (EU). The SDGs mentioned in the report include SDG 1 (No Poverty), SDG 2 (Zero Hunger), SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), and SDG 13 (Climate Action). Here, we assess these SDGs and their implications for the activities in the report and trade between the countries analyzed and the EU.

- **SDG 1. No Poverty:** The report emphasizes initiatives that enhance the livelihoods of farmers and workers in the South African wine industry, contributing to poverty reduction. Promoting fair labour practices and improving working conditions help lift workers out of poverty, ensuring better living standards and economic stability. Improved livelihoods and better working conditions can enhance the reputation of South African wine in the EU market, leading to increased demand and better market access. Aligning with SDG 1 helps South African wine producers meet the ethical and sustainability criteria European consumers prefer, fostering stronger trade relations.
- **SDG 2. Zero Hunger:** The initiatives aim to enhance agricultural productivity and sustainability, directly contributing to food security and promoting sustainable agriculture. Implementing sustainable farming practices ensures the

long-term viability of the wine industry, addressing food security concerns. Compliance with sustainable agricultural practices can make South African wine more attractive to EU consumers who prioritize sustainability, potentially increasing exports. Sustainable practices can differentiate South African wine in a competitive market, enhancing its appeal and market share in the EU.

- **SDG 8. Decent Work and Economic Growth:** Focus on improving labour conditions, ensuring fair wages, and promoting decent work environments. Enhancing labour standards and working conditions contributes to economic growth and stability in the wine industry. Meeting international labour standards can improve the reputation of South African wine in the EU market, aligning with consumer preferences for ethically produced goods. Fair labour practices can enhance productivity and quality, making South African wine more competitive globally.
- **SDG 12. Responsible Consumption and Production:** Efforts to promote sustainable farming practices and reduce waste in wine production align with responsible consumption and production goals. Emphasizing resource efficiency and sustainability in production processes reduces environmental impact and enhances long-term viability. Sustainable production practices increase the appeal of South African wine to environmentally conscious EU consumers. Meeting EU sustainability standards facilitates smoother trade processes and market access.
- **SDG 13. Climate Action:** Implementing practices that reduce greenhouse gas emissions and enhance climate resilience in viticulture. Promoting sustainable agricultural practices that adapt to and mitigate climate change impacts. EU consumers increasingly prefer products that contribute to climate action, enhancing the marketability of South African wine. Compliance with climate action initiatives can bolster the sustainability credentials of South African wine, improving its competitive edge in the EU market.

Legislative Framework

1. Domestic Legislation

- *Liquor Products Act No. 60 of 1989*

This Act governs the production, distribution, and sale of liquor products in South Africa. The Liquor Product Act ensures that all wine products undergo a certification process to verify quality and safety. The certification enhances consumer trust and ensures that South African wine meets domestic and international standards, which

is crucial for market acceptance in the EU. It specifies the labelling requirements for liquor products to ensure transparency and consumer information. The Act guarantees adherence to quality standards for maintaining consumer trust and market access domestically and internationally. Compliance with labelling standards ensures that South African wine can be sold in the EU market, where clear and accurate labelling is mandated.

- *National Environmental Management Act (NEMA) No. 107 of 1998*

The Environmental Management Act establishes principles for sustainable development and environmental management, including requirements for environmental impact assessments and conservation measures. An environmental impact assessment (EIA) is required for projects that may significantly affect the environment. Conducting EIAs for vineyard expansions or new wine production facilities ensures sustainable practices, aligning with EU environmental standards. Imposes a duty on parties to prevent environmental harm and mandates remediation if damage occurs. Compliance with this duty supports sustainable viticulture, making South African wine more attractive to eco-conscious European consumers. In South Africa, this promotes sustainable viticulture practices, which are necessary for aligning with international environmental standards and enhancing the market appeal of South African wine in eco-conscious markets.

- *Basic Conditions of Employment Act No. 75 of 1997*

The Employment Act governs basic employment conditions. It includes regulations on working hours, leave, remuneration, and termination of employment while ensuring fair labour practices within the wine industry. This is crucial for maintaining ethical standards and improving its reputation domestically and internationally. Amongst other things, it sets maximum working hours to ensure fair labour practices. Adherence to fair working hours helps improve labour conditions, which is important for ethical trade certifications and consumer trust in the EU. It also mandates a minimum amount of paid leave for employees. Providing adequate leave aligns with international labour standards, enhancing the industry's reputation for fair labour practices.

- *South African Labour Relations Act*

This Act ensures that all workers are treated fairly and their rights are protected. Upholding fair labour practices is crucial for maintaining ethical standards and

certifications valued in the EU market. The Act, amongst other things, provides employees with the right to strike under certain conditions, ensures fair labour dispute resolutions, and enhances workplace stability and ethical compliance, which is important for maintaining a positive industry image. In this context, the Act supports the implementation of ethical trade initiatives by ensuring fair treatment and rights for workers in the wine industry.

- *Consumer Protection Act*

This Act mandates that consumers be provided with complete and accurate product information. This generates transparency in product information, which in turn helps build consumer trust, which is essential for market acceptance in the EU. This improves the marketability of South African wine by ensuring transparent and honest labelling and marketing.

2. European Framework

- *EU Regulation 2018/848 on Organic Production and Labelling of Organic Products*

This Regulation establishes the overall goals and guiding principles for organic production. Adhering to these principles allows South African wine to be labelled and marketed as organic in the EU, meeting consumer demand for organic products. The Regulation also outlines the requirements for the control and certification of organic products, which facilitates overseeing whether South African organic wine complies with EU standards, facilitating market entry and consumer confidence. Compliance with this Regulation allows South African wine to be marketed as organic in the EU, tapping into the growing demand for organic products and expanding market access.

- *EU Directive 2014/95/EU (Non-Financial Reporting Directive)*

This Directive requires large companies to report on their environmental, social, and governance (ESG) practices. In this case, it encourages South African wine producers to adopt and transparently report on sustainable and ethical practices, enhancing their appeal to European investors and consumers.

- *EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)*

The GDPR establishes critical principles for data protection, including lawfulness, fairness, and transparency. Compliance with GDPR ensures that South African

exporters manage personal data responsibly, maintain trust with EU customers and avoid legal penalties. The GDPR specifies the information that must be provided to individuals when their data is collected. This helps build transparency and consumer trust, crucial for maintaining business relationships in the EU.

3. International Framework

- *International Labour Organization (ILO) Conventions*

The ILO Conventions set international labour standards to guarantee fair labour practices and improve working conditions. Aligning South African labour practices with international standards enhances the credibility and ethical standing of the wine industry.

- *Convention No. 138: Minimum Age Convention*

This Convention sets the minimum age for employment at 15 years. Complying with such a Convention should ensure that South African wine producers do not employ underage workers, aligning with international labour standards.

- *Convention No. 182: Worst Forms of Child Labour Convention*

This Convention calls for the prohibition and elimination of the worst forms of child labour. Compliance with this Convention supports ethical certifications and enhances the reputation of South African wine in the EU market.

- *United Nations Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UNGPs)*

The Principles promote responsible business practices and human rights protections. They provide a framework for business ethics and encourage adherence to human rights standards, which are crucial for maintaining international trade relationships and ethical certification. In doing so, they require businesses to avoid infringing on human rights and address adverse impacts. Adopting these principles ensures that South African wine producers adhere to human rights standards, which are critical for maintaining ethical certifications and consumer trust.

- **World Trade Organization (WTO) Agreements**

- *Sanitary and Phytosanitary (SPS) Agreement*

This Agreement hopes to ensure food safety and animal/plant health standards. In this context, the Agreement helps South African wine meet international safety standards, facilitating smoother trade and market access.

- *Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT) Agreement*

The Agreement aims to ensure that technical regulations do not create unnecessary trade obstacles. Compliance with these regulations helps South African wine producers meet international standards, promoting smoother trade relations with the EU.

Compliance with all these agreements facilitates smoother trade processes and market access, ensuring South African wine meets global standards.

Impact on Trade Between South Africa and the European Union

The integration of these SDGs into the South African wine industry has several significant implications for trade between South Africa and the EU:

- **Enhanced Market Access:** Compliance with SDGs and associated ethical and sustainability standards improves market access in the EU, where consumers and regulators prioritize these values. Such compliance enhances trade opportunities and market penetration in the EU, fostering economic growth and sustainability in the South African wine industry.
- **Improved Reputation:** Aligning with international standards on labour, environmental practices, and sustainability enhances the reputation of South African wine, making it more attractive to European consumers. This builds brand trust and loyalty, increasing demand and market share in the EU.
- **Trade Relationships:** Strengthening ethical and sustainable practices fosters stronger trade relationships with the EU, facilitating smoother trade negotiations and reducing trade barriers. This facilitates smoother trade negotiations and reduces barriers, promoting long-term trade partnerships.
- **Competitiveness:** Adopting sustainable and ethical practices enhances the overall competitiveness of South African wine in the global market, helping it

stand out in a crowded market. This differentiates South African wine from competitors, potentially increasing exports and economic benefits.

Impact on Trade Between South Africa and the European Union

- *Compliance and Market Access:* Adhering to EU regulations, such as those on organic production and labelling, ensures South African wine can access the EU market without facing regulatory barriers.
- *Sustainability and Ethical Standards:* Embracing international labour standards and sustainability initiatives improves the global reputation of South African wine, making it more attractive to European consumers who value ethical and sustainable products.
- *Economic Partnership Agreements (EPAs):* These agreements, like the SADC-EU EPA, provide preferential access to the EU market, reducing tariffs and enhancing competitiveness.

Unaddressed Areas of Law

- *Intellectual Property Law:* There is no mention of protections related to branding, trademarks, or geographical indications, which are crucial for market differentiation and protection against counterfeit products. This aspect is critical for market differentiation and protection against counterfeit products.
- *Competition Law:* The report does not discuss regulations preventing anti-competitive practices vital for maintaining fair market conditions. This is vital for maintaining fair market conditions and fostering a competitive industry environment.
- *Taxation Law:* There is no analysis of the tax implications for wine production and exports, which can significantly impact profitability and pricing strategies. This significantly impacts profitability and pricing strategies, which are crucial for market success.
- *Contract Law:* Details on contracts within the supply chain, including agreements with distributors and retailers, are not addressed. This matters because contract law ensures clear, enforceable agreements that facilitate smooth business operations and reduce legal risks.

Final Remarks

This legal framework analysis illustrates the regulatory environment impacting the South African wine industry. It highlights the importance of compliance with domestic, European, and international laws to maintain market access, promote sustainable and ethical practices, and enhance competitiveness in the global market.

Case Study #13

Dairy production, standards and competitiveness in global markets

Lead organization & name of lead contact: CRPA –

Authors: Alberto Menghi, Lorena Giglio, Serena Soffiantini, Stefano Pignedoli, Annunziata Palamara, Dorothee Boelling* Andrea Bassi**, Marco Guzzetti**

Analysis of the Legal Framework within the Dairy Production Case Study

Introduction

The case study report titled "Dairy production, standards and competitiveness in global markets" investigates the impact of labour conditions and costs on the competitiveness of dairy products in international trade. This study includes countries from Africa (Algeria, South Africa, Zimbabwe), America (Argentina, Brazil, United States of America), and Europe (France, Germany, Italy). It emphasizes the relationship between labour legislation in the dairy sector and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) Assessment

The case study references several SDGs, highlighting their importance in promoting sustainable development in the dairy sector.

- **SDG 1. No Poverty:** Labour legislation reduces poverty and improves livelihoods by ensuring fair wages and decent working conditions. Enhanced worker protections and fair wages in the dairy sector improve economic stability for workers and their families, reducing poverty levels. Countries with strong labour laws attract better trade relationships with the EU, which prioritizes ethical labour practices.
- **SDG 2. Zero Hunger:** The dairy sector is critical in the food system. Labour laws supporting sustainable practices ensure food safety and quality standards. Sustainable agricultural practices lead to higher-quality dairy products and improved food security. Compliance with food safety standards facilitates

smoother trade with the EU, with stringent requirements for imported food products.

- **SDG 3. Good Health and Well-being:** Labour laws ensure workplace safety and health standards, which contribute to the well-being of dairy workers. Improved health and safety standards reduce workplace injuries and illnesses, enhancing productivity. Better health and safety conditions align with EU standards, making it easier for countries to trade with the EU.
- **SDG 8. Decent Work and Economic Growth:** Labour legislation aligns with SDG 8, promoting inclusive economic growth, productive employment, and decent work. Ensures fair wages, safe working conditions, and equal opportunities, fostering a more sustainable and productive dairy sector. Countries adhering to these standards are more likely to establish strong trade relations with the EU, which values ethical labour practices.
- **SDG 6. Clean Water and Sanitation:** Environmental regulations in the dairy sector ensure sustainable use of water resources. It also promotes efficient water use and reduces pollution, ensuring the long-term sustainability of dairy farming. Sustainable water practices are increasingly important for accessing markets like the EU, which prioritize environmental sustainability.
- **SDG 13. Climate Action:** Environmental regulations aim to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and promote sustainable farming practices. It encourages adopting practices that mitigate climate change, such as reducing emissions and improving energy efficiency. Alignment with climate action goals enhances market access to the EU, which emphasizes environmental sustainability in trade policies.
- **SDG 15. Life on Land:** Sustainable agricultural practices protect biodiversity and ecosystems. Ensures the preservation of ecosystems and promotes biodiversity through responsible land use. Compliance with environmental standards is crucial for accessing the EU market, which values biodiversity and ecosystem protection.

Legislative Framework

1. Domestic Laws

Europe:

The European countries in the study adhere to stringent labour laws ensuring decent work conditions, fair wages, and comprehensive social security benefits. For instance, Germany has robust mechanisms for worker protection, including significant severance pay and unemployment benefits.

France

Labour laws include the Labour Code, which ensures worker protection, fair wages, and extensive social benefits. Specific provisions include mandatory paid leave, maximum working hours, and conditions for overtime pay. The Labour Code defines maximum working hours and conditions for overtime. It ensures the right to paid leave. Also, it Prohibits child labour under the age of 16, with specific conditions for apprenticeships. The Labour Code aims to ensure fair working conditions and is critical for maintaining high labour standards in dairy production

Germany

The Works Constitution Act and the Social Security Code provide comprehensive protections, including detailed severance pay structures and unemployment benefits. Provisions also include mandatory health and safety regulations and collective bargaining rights.

The Works Constitution Act (*Betriebsverfassungsgesetz*) establishes specifically the co-determination rights for work hours, including overtime regulations. It also mandates social plans for economic restructuring, affecting severance pay.

On the other hand, the Social Security Code (*Sozialgesetzbuch*) defines wage calculations for social security contributions. These regulations provide robust worker protections, ensuring fair wages and comprehensive benefits.

Italy

The Italian Labour Law includes protections such as minimum wage requirements, provisions for maternity and paternity leave, and specific working hour regulations.

Italy's Social Security Law also provides extensive coverage for health care and unemployment benefits.

The Labour Law (Statuto dei Lavoratori) ensures job security and fair wages, provides for maternity and paternity leave, and defines minimum wage standards. These laws protect workers' rights, ensuring decent working conditions and fair compensation.

United States

Labour laws provide for health care and long-term disability insurance, but severance pay is not mandated at the federal level. Also, Environmental regulations are robust, focusing on emissions and sustainable agricultural practices.

- *Fair Labor Standards Act (FLSA)*

The Act establishes minimum wage, overtime pay eligibility, recordkeeping, and child labour standards. The FLSA covers full-time and part-time workers in the private sector and federal, state, and local governments. In addition to **the** minimum wage, the Act deals with overtime pay, recordkeeping, and child labour standards. The instrument ensures basic worker protection, which is vital for maintaining fair labour conditions in the dairy sector.

- *Occupational Safety and Health Act (OSHA)*

The OSHA Act ensures worker and workplace safety by setting and enforcing standards and providing training, outreach, education, and assistance. Amongst the standards, **the OSHA** Promotes safe working environments, reducing occupational hazards in dairy production.

- *Clean Air Act (CAA)*

The CAA Regulates air emissions from stationary and mobile sources. The Act authorizes the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) to establish National Ambient Air Quality Standards to protect public health and the environment. It establishes the basic structure for regulating discharges of pollutants into the waters of the United States and regulating quality standards for surface waters. Moreover, it regulates air and water emissions, setting quality standards for protecting public health and the environment.

- *Clean Water Act (CWA)*

The CWA regulates discharges into US waters. It establishes water quality standards and ensures environmental protection in dairy production, aligning with sustainability goals.

Africa:

Labour laws vary significantly, with South Africa having relatively strong protections and benefits, while Algeria and Zimbabwe offer less comprehensive worker benefits.

Algeria

Algerian Labour laws mandate a 40-48 hour workweek, with specific provisions for sick leave and workplace injury pay. However, enforcement and coverage of the laws can be inconsistent. More specifically, they mandate a 40-48 hour workweek while also providing for paid sick leave. They aim to ensure basic worker protections but face challenges in enforcement.

South Africa

The Basic Conditions of Employment Act (BCEA) regulates working hours, leave, and termination of employment. The Labour Relations Act (LRA) governs collective bargaining and worker protections.

The Basic Conditions of Employment Act (BCEA) specifically regulates maximum working hours and Mandates annual leave entitlements. It provides comprehensive worker protections, aligning with international labour standards.

The Labour Relations Act (LRA) aims to ensure collective bargaining rights. The main objective is to strengthen worker representation and rights in the workplace.

Zimbabwe

The Labour Act establishes minimum wage and working hour regulations in Zimbabwe and provides termination conditions and severance pay. However, the enforcement and actual conditions can significantly differ from legal standards. Generally, it sets basic labour standards, but implementation varies widely.

South America (Argentina and Brazil)

Both countries have legal frameworks providing health care and unemployment benefits, though enforcement and coverage can be inconsistent.

Argentina

In Argentina, labour laws ensure minimum wage and maximum working hours and provide comprehensive health care and unemployment benefits through various social security schemes. The Labour Law (Ley de Contrato de Trabajo) Defines working hours and sets minimum wage standards. It aims to protect workers' rights, ensuring fair wages and conditions in the dairy industry.

Brazil

The Consolidation of Labour Laws (CLT) governs employment conditions, including minimum wage, working hours, health and safety standards, and social security benefits. Specifically, the Consolidation of Labour Laws (CLT) regulates working hours and establishes minimum wage. It seeks to govern employment conditions, promoting fair labour practices.

Africa and South America:

Environmental regulations vary by country. In many African countries, environmental standards are less stringent, impacting their competitiveness and environmental footprint. South American countries like Argentina and Brazil have more robust frameworks but face challenges in enforcement. Environmental regulations vary, impacting competitiveness and sustainability. Countries with less stringent standards face challenges in enforcement and market access.

2. European Framework

European Union Policies

The EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) significantly impacts dairy production, providing subsidies and incentives for sustainable practices. These policies aim to ensure food security, improve competitiveness, and promote environmental sustainability. Strict environmental regulations, including emission standards and sustainable farming practices, impact dairy production. These regulations drive higher costs but also promote sustainable development.

- ***EU Directives on Environmental Protection***

These include the Nitrates Directive, the Water Framework Directive, and the Habitats Directive. These directives mandate sustainable farming practices, limit emissions, and protect biodiversity, directly impacting dairy production practices.

➤ **Nitrates Directive (Directive 91/676/EEC)**

This Directive mandates action programs for nitrate pollution and requires measures to control and reduce nitrate levels.

➤ **Water Framework Directive (Directive 2000/60/EC)**

The Directive establishes objectives for good water status. It also lists basic measures for water management.

➤ **Habitats Directive (Directive 92/43/EEC)**

The instrument details conservation measures.

These directives enforce sustainable farming practices, impacting dairy production.

○ *Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) - Regulation (EU) No 1307/2013*

The Cap provides financial support and subsidies for sustainable agricultural practices, including those in the dairy sector. The CAP's cross-compliance mechanism ensures farmers adhere to environmental regulations to receive payments. The CAP's environmental measures promote sustainable land use and reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Therefore, it grants financial support for farmers adhering to sustainable practices, enhancing competitiveness. It establishes greening payment for environmental benefits and sets ecological focus area requirements. By supporting sustainable practices, the CAP aims to improve the market.

The EU's stringent import standards affect international trade, with non-EU countries needing to meet these standards to access the EU market.

○ ***Regulations on Animal Welfare - Regulation (EC) No 178/2002***

The EU has strict regulations on animal welfare, which impact dairy farming practices. Compliance with these regulations ensures access to the EU market but increases production costs. Impact dairy farming practices, ensuring access to the EU market but increasing production costs. The Regulation establishes general requirements for food safety and traceability of food.

This Regulation ensures high standards for imported dairy products, influencing global trade practices.

- *EU Import Standards*

Non-EU countries must comply with stringent safety, quality, and environmental standards to export dairy products to the EU, creating trade barriers but driving improvements in production practices. These standards cover sanitary and phytosanitary measures (SPS) to protect animal and human health.

3. International Framework

International Labour Organization (ILO)

The ILO's conventions influence labour laws in the countries studied, especially concerning workers' rights, safety, and working conditions.

- *ILO Conventions No. 87 and 98*

These conventions protect the rights to freedom of association and collective bargaining, crucial for improving labour conditions in the dairy sector. The ILO's standards influence national labour laws in the case study countries. Protect rights to freedom of association and collective bargaining, improving labour conditions in the dairy sector.

More specifically, Convention No. 87 (Freedom of Association and Protection of the Right to Organise) protects workers' rights to form and join organizations to ensure fundamental labour rights, impacting worker conditions in the dairy sector.

On the other hand, Convention No. 98 (Right to Organise and Collective Bargaining) promotes collective bargaining to enhance labour rights and negotiations, improving working conditions.

- *Convention No. 129 (Labour Inspection – Agriculture)*

This Convention focuses on labour inspection in agriculture, ensuring fair labour practices and safe working conditions. It establishes explicit conditions for inspections of labour conditions and enforces fair labour practices and safety in agriculture.

World Trade Organization (WTO)

WTO agreements on agriculture and trade liberalization impact the dairy trade, setting rules for tariffs, subsidies, and trade barriers. Compliance with these agreements affects competitiveness and market access.

- *Agreement on Agriculture (AoA)*

The AoA sets out rules for market access, domestic support, and export subsidies for agricultural products. The AoA influences tariff structures and trade policies, impacting dairy trade competitiveness. More specifically, it defines market access commitments and domestic support commitments.

- *Sanitary and Phytosanitary Measures (SPS Agreement)*

The SPS Agreement ensures that member countries' food safety and animal and plant health regulations are based on scientific principles necessary for market access. Compliance with SPS measures is necessary for market access, affecting international trade dynamics. More importantly, the SPS Agreement sets out conditions for risk assessment and determination of appropriate levels of protection. This Agreement also helps ensure food safety and animal health, which is critical for market access.

Impact on Trade between Case Study Countries and the EU

Competitiveness:

- *European Countries:* Farmers benefit from CAP subsidies and support, enhancing competitiveness. However, high labour costs and stringent environmental regulations increase production costs, impacting their ability to compete globally.
- *United States and Argentina:* Lower production costs and large-scale operations enhance competitiveness. However, they face challenges in meeting EU standards.
- *South Africa and Brazil:* Competitive advantages include lower labour costs. However, environmental and labour standards may hinder access to the EU market due to strict compliance requirements.

Trade Barriers and Opportunities:

- *EU's Import Standards:* Non-EU countries must meet high standards for safety, quality, and environmental sustainability to export to the EU, creating trade barriers and driving improvements in production practices.
- *Tariffs and Quotas:* WTO rules and bilateral agreements influence tariffs and quotas, affecting trade volumes and market access. The balance of tariffs and subsidies can significantly impact competitiveness and trade dynamics.

Areas of Law Not Addressed in the Report

- *Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)*: The report does not discuss the impact of IPR on dairy production and trade, such as patents on dairy processing technologies or trademarks on dairy products.
- *Consumer Protection Laws*: Regulations ensuring the protection of consumers, particularly concerning food safety and labelling, are not extensively covered.
- *Corporate Governance and Compliance*: The report does not address how corporate governance standards and compliance requirements affect the operations of dairy producers in different countries.

Final Remarks

A combination of domestic laws, EU policies, and international agreements influences the legal framework within which dairy production operates. These regulations significantly impact dairy products' competitiveness, sustainability, and trade dynamics. Addressing gaps in intellectual property rights, consumer protection, and corporate governance could enhance understanding of the legal landscape affecting the dairy industry. Finally, the study highlights the complexity of international trade and the need for compliance with a range of legal and regulatory standards to ensure competitive and sustainable dairy production.

Case Study #14

Governing Trade to Influence Land-use and Food Systems Pathways: The Expansion of Soy-meat Complex in the MATOPIBA Brazilian Frontier

Lead Organization & name of lead contact: Universidad Politécnica de Madrid.
Team: Matheus Alvez Zanella, Maria Bustamante, Pablo Vidueira, Maddalena Bettoni, Cintya Manrique

Analysis of the Legal Framework in the Context of the Case Study

Introduction

The case study focuses on the expansion of the soy-meat complex in the MATOPIBA region of Brazil, examining how trade-related measures can govern this expansion to promote sustainable development. This analysis assesses the impact of domestic, European, and international laws on the activities studied and the influence of this legal framework on trade between Brazil and the European Union (EU). Additionally, it identifies areas of law not addressed in the report.

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

- **SDG 15. Life on Land:** Efforts to eradicate illegal deforestation and promote the sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems are central to SDG 15. The Brazilian Forestry Code and EU regulations align with this goal by setting legal frameworks to protect natural habitats and biodiversity. Compliance with SDG 15 requires Brazilian exporters to adhere to stringent environmental standards to maintain access to the EU market. This alignment promotes sustainable trade practices and environmental conservation.
- **SDG 13. Climate Action:** Measures to combat climate change through sustainable agricultural practices are highlighted in the report. The EU's Regulation (EU) 2023/1115 and the Forestry Code's provisions aim to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by preventing deforestation. Sustainable practices reduce the carbon footprint of agricultural products, making them more acceptable to environmentally conscious markets like the EU. This fosters trade relations based on shared climate action goals.

- **SDG 17. Partnerships for the Goals:** The development of multi-actor territorial agreements fosters partnerships for sustainable development. These collaborations involve government, civil society, and the private sector working together to achieve sustainability goals. Strong partnerships enhance the implementation of sustainable practices, improving compliance with international standards and facilitating smoother trade relations. Such partnerships are crucial for addressing complex challenges like deforestation and promoting inclusive economic growth.

Legislative Framework

1. Domestic Laws

- *Brazil's Forestry Code (Law 12.651/2012)*

The Forestry Code mandates the preservation of Permanent Protection Areas (APPs) and Legal Reserves (RLs). APPs include ecologically sensitive areas such as riverbanks, hilltops, and slopes that must be preserved to maintain environmental stability. RLs are specific portions of rural properties that must be set aside for native vegetation preservation. The preservation requirements are:

- Up to 80% in the Amazon;
- 35% in most of Maranhão State;
- 20% in the rest of Matopiba's Cerrado.

Enforcement of these provisions is weak, leading to significant illegal deforestation. Transparency and accountability issues in the ASV process contribute to this problem

The Forestry Code also establishes the conditions for the Authorization of Native Vegetation Conversion (ASVs). Any land conversion requires ASVs issued by relevant authorities, typically the Environmental Agencies of Brazilian States. This process is designed to ensure that land conversion activities meet environmental standards. The process is criticized for its lack of transparency and accountability, which leads to illegal deforestation. The report notes that up to 94% of deforestation in regions like the Amazon and Matopiba is illegal due to these enforcement issues. Land conversion requires ASVs, but the process is often opaque and poorly enforced, contributing to illegal activities.

Lastly, the Forestry Code defines what it understands for Green Grabbing. Farmers may declare non-titled, well-preserved land as part of their RLs to comply with the

Code, which displaces traditional communities. This practice, facilitated by the Rural Environmental Registry (CAR) reforms in 2012, allows for declaring RLs on non-contiguous lands. This has led to "green grabbing," where commercial interests claim lands traditionally occupied by rural communities. Declining non-titled, well-preserved land as RLs to comply with the Code displaces traditional communities.

The Forestry Code's provisions aim to protect biodiversity and regulate land use, but enforcement challenges mar its implementation. These issues affect the sustainability of the soy-meat complex by allowing illegal deforestation to continue, undermining efforts to achieve more sustainable agricultural practices.

2. European Framework

- *Regulation (EU) 2023/1115*

The Regulation addresses the availability of certain commodities and products associated with deforestation on the Union market and exports from the Union, repealing Regulation (EU) No 995/2010. The goal is to prevent deforestation-related commodities from entering the EU market. The Regulation establishes obligations for operators and traders to ensure that commodities and products placed on the EU market or exported from it are not associated with deforestation or forest degradation. This Regulation directly impacts the soy-meat complex in Matopiba by requiring that soy exported to the EU does not contribute to deforestation. It introduces due diligence requirements for operators, including the need for robust traceability and transparency measures. Operators must collect and retain information on the supply chain, including the country of production, geo-location coordinates, and other relevant data. The Regulation emphasizes the need for transparency and traceability in the supply chain, pressuring Brazilian soy producers to provide detailed information about their production practices.

Moreover, it provides for risk assessment and mitigation procedures that operators must follow to ensure compliance with the Regulation. This requires operators to actively assess and mitigate risks related to deforestation, which affects how soy is produced and traded. Finally, the Regulation outlines the responsibilities of EU member states in enforcing the Regulation, including the designation of competent authorities and the implementation of penalties for non-compliance. This means that through enforcement by member states, the Regulation provides a framework for compliance and penalties and indirectly influences Brazilian practices. Some obligations for operators regarding the documentation and reporting of their due diligence systems and the effectiveness of their measures illustrate such outreach of

the Regulation. This matters especially concerning how thorough documentation and reporting impact how Brazilian exporters manage and report their compliance efforts.

- *European Union's Deforestation-Free Supply Chain Initiative*

The initiative aims to ensure that products placed on the EU market do not contribute to deforestation. This includes soy, beef, palm oil, wood, cocoa, and coffee products. Companies must implement due diligence procedures to trace the origin of commodities, assess deforestation risks, and take steps to mitigate those risks. These obligations enforce sustainable practices in supply chains, affecting Brazilian exports to the EU. Companies must submit regular reports detailing their supply chain practices and compliance with the Regulation's requirements. This includes providing evidence of the sustainability of their sourcing practices. This requirement enhances transparency and accountability in the supply chain, promoting sustainable practices among Brazilian producers. Enhanced traceability requirements obligate companies to provide detailed information about the source of their products, ensuring that they can verify that no deforestation has occurred. Traceability requirements impact how Brazilian soy is produced and verified, ensuring compliance with EU standards.

These EU regulations aim to curb deforestation by enforcing stringent requirements on imports, promoting transparency, and holding companies accountable. This creates pressure on Brazilian producers to adhere to sustainable practices to access the EU market, indirectly influencing land-use policies in Matopiba.

3. International Framework

- *Glasgow Leaders' Declaration on Forests and Land Use (2021)*

The Glasgow Declaration emphasizes international cooperation and shared responsibility in addressing deforestation, reinforcing commitments made at COP26. The declaration commits signatory countries to halt and reverse forest loss and land degradation by 2030 while delivering sustainable development and promoting an inclusive rural transformation. This alignment with global sustainability goals influences Brazilian and EU policies, promoting sustainable agricultural practices. The declaration also aligns with the goals of the case study by promoting sustainable agricultural practices and reinforcing international commitments to combat deforestation.

Impact on Trade and Activities

- *Influence of Domestic Law:* If effectively enforced, the Forestry Code's provisions could significantly reduce illegal deforestation and promote sustainable

land use. However, enforcement issues undermine these potential benefits, allowing unsustainable practices to persist.

- *Influence of EU Legislation:* EU regulations create external pressure on Brazil to improve sustainability in its agricultural practices. Compliance with these regulations is essential for Brazilian soy producers to maintain access to the lucrative EU market.
- *International Commitments:* The Glasgow Declaration and similar international agreements reinforce the need for sustainable practices, aligning global trade policies with environmental objectives.

Areas of Law Not Addressed

- *Human Rights and Labor Laws:* The report does not extensively cover laws protecting labour rights and preventing exploitation within the soy-meat complex.
- *Intellectual Property and Agricultural Innovation:* Legal frameworks governing agricultural biotechnology, patents, and innovation in sustainable farming practices are not discussed.
- *Water Rights and Management:* While water grabbing is mentioned, the legal instruments governing water rights and management in agricultural contexts are not detailed.
- *Consumer Protection Laws:* The impact of consumer protection laws in Brazil and the EU on promoting sustainable and ethical consumption has not been explored.

Final Remarks

A combination of domestic, European, and international laws influences the legal framework governing the expansion of the soy-meat complex in Matopiba. While these laws collectively aim to promote sustainable practices and curb deforestation, their effectiveness is hindered by enforcement challenges and gaps in specific legal areas. The EU's stringent regulations pressure Brazilian producers to comply with sustainability standards, impacting trade dynamics between Brazil and the EU. Addressing the identified gaps in human rights, labour laws, intellectual property, water management, and consumer protection could further enhance the legal framework's ability to support sustainable development in the region.

Case Study #15

Agricultural trade, food systems and ecological resilience in North Africa

Lead organization & name of lead contact: Transnational Institute (TNI); Pietje Vervest and Sylvia Kay

Analysis of the Legal Framework Impacting Agricultural Trade Between Tunisia and the EU

The case study of agricultural trade between Tunisia and the European Union (EU), mainly focusing on the olive oil sector, operates within a complex legal framework involving domestic, European, and international laws. This framework significantly influences the activities and outcomes of agricultural trade, shaping both the opportunities and challenges Tunisia faces.

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and Their Impact

Assessment of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in the Report

The "Olive Oil and Water: Moving towards sustainable agricultural trade between the EU and Tunisia" case study report references several Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and their related indicators. These SDGs provide a framework to assess the broader impacts of the legal and policy measures on Tunisia's agricultural sector and its trade relations with the EU.

- **SDG 1: No Poverty:** The report highlights the socio-economic challenges faced by small and medium-sized farmers in Tunisia, including limited access to financial resources and support services. The focus on export-oriented agriculture under the current trade agreements with the EU has led to the marginalization of small farmers, exacerbating poverty in rural areas. Reducing poverty requires targeted support for these farmers, improving their access to resources, and ensuring fair prices for their produce. Policies that aim to reduce poverty can lead to more equitable trade relations by ensuring that trade benefits are distributed fairly among all stakeholders, including small farmers. Improved economic conditions for smallholders can enhance their productivity and competitiveness in the EU market, leading to a more balanced trade relationship.

- **SDG 2. Zero Hunger:** The report discusses the impact of trade agreements on Tunisia's focus on export crops like olive oil at the expense of subsistence crops, leading to increased dependency on food imports. This shift has implications for food security as the country becomes vulnerable to global market fluctuations and crises. Ensuring sustainable food production systems can improve Tunisia's self-sufficiency and resilience, reducing the need for imports and enabling more stable export flows to the EU. Trade policies that support sustainable practices can also enhance the quality and marketability of Tunisian agricultural products in the EU.
- **SDG 6. Clean Water and Sanitation:** The report highlights the significant water usage in olive oil production, noting that intensive irrigation practices are unsustainable given Tunisia's limited water resources. Efficient water use is crucial for maintaining agricultural productivity and sustainability. Improved water-use efficiency can lead to more sustainable agricultural practices, ensuring long-term productivity and meeting domestic and export demands. Sustainable water management practices can enhance the reputation of Tunisian agricultural products in the EU market, potentially leading to better trade terms and higher demand.
- **SDG 10. Reduced Inequalities:** The report critiques the unequal trade provisions under the Association Agreement and the proposed DCFTA with the EU, which favour EU products and impose restrictive conditions on Tunisian exports. Addressing these inequalities is essential for fair trade relations. Implementing fair trade practices and ensuring differential treatment for Tunisia can improve market access for Tunisian products in the EU. This can lead to increased exports, higher incomes for farmers, and overall economic development, contributing to reduced inequalities between Tunisia and the EU.

Legislative Framework

1. Domestic Legislation

- *The 2014 Constitution of Tunisia*

The Tunisian Constitution underpins Tunisia's commitment to sustainable resource management and equitable access to resources, both essential for a resilient agricultural sector. Ensuring sustainable use and equitable natural resource distribution supports food security and environmental sustainability. The Constitution establishes that natural resources belong to the people and mandates state sovereignty over these resources to ensure their exploitation benefits the national economy and promotes sustainable development. Also, it guarantees the right to water, recognizing it

as a human right and obligating the state to preserve and rationalize its use for future generations.

The Constitution also defines natural resources as belonging to the people and mandates state sovereignty over these resources to ensure their exploitation benefits the national economy and promotes sustainable development. The report mentions this article to discuss Tunisia's commitment to sustainable resource management, highlighting the state's role in ensuring that agricultural practices benefit the broader economy and promote sustainability. Finally, in guaranteeing the right to water, recognizing it as a human right and obligating the state to preserve and rationalize its use for future generations, the report underscores the need for sustainable water management practices in the olive oil sector.

- *Law No. 76-85 (Tunisian Forestry Code)*

This law is fundamental in forest management and conservation, indirectly supporting agricultural sustainability by maintaining the ecological balance necessary for agriculture. It focuses on forest management and conservation, indirectly supporting agricultural sustainability by maintaining the ecological balance necessary for agriculture. The report highlights the law's importance in forest management and conservation, which supports agricultural sustainability by maintaining ecological balance. The law is also essential in sustainable land and resource management, crucial for long-term agricultural productivity.

- *Law No. 2009-49 (Integrated Coastal Zone Management)*

This law focuses on regulating land use to prevent urban sprawl and preserve agricultural land, ensuring that prime agricultural lands remain available for food production. It shows the importance of protecting prime agricultural lands for food production, ensuring food security and sustainable agricultural practices.

These domestic laws collectively aim to safeguard natural resources, ensure sustainable agricultural practices, and support small and medium-sized farmers, which are pivotal to Tunisia's agricultural output. Effective land use regulation and forest conservation are crucial to maintaining agricultural productivity and resilience.

2. European and International Framework

- *1994 WTO Agreement on Agriculture*

Based on this Agreement, Tunisia must reduce import tariffs on agricultural products, facilitating more significant international trade. The report discusses how Tunisia's obligations under this article require it to reduce import tariffs, which impacts domestic farmers by increasing competition from international producers. This includes reforming domestic agricultural support mechanisms and reducing subsidies that could distort trade. The report critiques the reduction of agricultural input subsidies in Tunisia, which has affected small and medium-sized farmers by reducing the support they receive from the government. Also, it is essential to note that although limited due to Tunisia's developing country status, the Agreement imposes some constraints on export subsidies. While Tunisia's commitments here are limited due to its developing country status, the report mentions the constraints this article places on export subsidies, which could otherwise support Tunisian agricultural exports.

This Agreement promotes trade liberalization, integrating Tunisian agriculture into global markets and exposing it to competition from more developed countries with significant agricultural subsidies.

- *1995 Association Agreement between Tunisia and the EU*

The Agreement calls for the full liberalization of industrial products by 2008 and the gradual liberalization of agricultural products and fisheries. It grants tariff privileges to Tunisian products within specific quotas and periods, aiming to balance trade benefits. The report highlights this as limiting Tunisia's benefits from the Agreement, with quotas and restrictive conditions that hinder competitive access to Tunisian products. It also eliminates customs duties on European products exported to Tunisia, including vegetable oils, cereals, and potato seeds. The report notes how this exacerbates the trade imbalance by making it easier for European products to enter the Tunisian market, thus increasing competition for local producers.

This Agreement has deeply influenced Tunisia's agricultural policies, encouraging an export-oriented approach. However, it has also been critiqued for favouring EU products through non-tariff barriers and restrictive conditions, which can disadvantage Tunisian farmers.

- *Proposed Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Agreement (DCFTA)*

The DCFTA includes chapters on sanitary and phytosanitary standards (SPS), intellectual property rights (IPR), and investor-state dispute settlement (ISDS). The report raises concerns about the potential impact of the DCFTA on Tunisian agriculture, particularly the risks posed to small and medium enterprises and labour rights, highlighting the broader implications for Tunisia's economic dependency and food sovereignty.

Overall Impact on Trade

Combining these legal frameworks creates a complex environment for Tunisia's agricultural trade. The liberalization policies, while opening up markets, have led to increased competition with subsidized EU agricultural products, affecting the profitability and sustainability of Tunisian agriculture. The emphasis on export-oriented production, particularly in the olive oil sector, has diverted focus from subsistence farming, impacting food security and local consumption patterns.

The SDGs provide a comprehensive framework for evaluating and improving the sustainability and equity of agricultural trade between Tunisia and the EU. Achieving these goals requires coordinated efforts to address the socio-economic, environmental, and trade policy challenges highlighted in the report.

Economic Impact:

- *Poverty Reduction:* Supporting small and medium-sized farmers through fair trade practices and targeted policies can enhance their economic stability, reducing poverty and increasing agricultural productivity.
- *Food Security:* Balancing export-oriented agriculture with the need for domestic food production can enhance food security and reduce dependency on volatile global markets.

Environmental Impact:

- *Sustainable Practices:* Promoting sustainable agricultural practices and efficient resource use can improve the resilience and sustainability of Tunisia's agricultural sector, ensuring long-term productivity and environmental health.

Social Impact:

- *Reduced Inequalities:* Ensuring fair trade terms and support for marginalized farmers can reduce socio-economic inequalities, promoting more inclusive economic growth and development.

Trade Relations:

- *Improved Market Access:* Implementing the SDGs can enhance the quality and competitiveness of Tunisian agricultural products, improve their marketability in the EU, and lead to more balanced and mutually beneficial trade relations.

Unaddressed Areas of Law

The report does not comprehensively address several areas of law, including:

- *Labour Laws:* Impact on agricultural labour rights and conditions, particularly under new trade agreements.
- *Consumer Protection Laws:* Ensuring local consumers are protected from price volatility and have access to affordable, nutritious food.
- *Intellectual Property Laws:* The Report does not focus on how these laws affect agricultural innovation and the protection of local varieties and knowledge.

Final Remarks

The legal framework governing agricultural trade between Tunisia and the EU significantly impacts Tunisia's agricultural sector. While international and European agreements have opened markets and integrated Tunisia into global trade networks, they have also introduced competition, resource management, and food security challenges. Domestic laws are crucial in mitigating these challenges by promoting sustainable practices and protecting resources. However, to fully support Tunisia's agricultural sector, there is a need for comprehensive policies that address all aspects of agricultural sustainability, labour rights, consumer protection, and intellectual property.

Concluding Remarks

The synthesis of findings from the 15 case studies presented in this report highlights the complex interplay between legal frameworks, agricultural practices, and sustainable trade. The diversity of case studies – from coffee production in Uganda to bio-ethanol trade between Brazil and the EU – illustrates the varying levels of engagement with legal and institutional issues, often reflecting each study's different focuses, methodologies, and empirical settings. Across these cases, several conclusions emerge about the challenges and opportunities in aligning legal frameworks with sustainable agricultural trade and development goals.

A notable finding from the case studies is the uneven attention given to various areas of law, such as, for example, patents, trademarks, and geographical indications (GIs). While these areas are crucial for fostering innovation and ensuring fair competition, they often received little attention in many case studies. A potential rationale for this gap relates to the data collection methods employed in the studies. Specifically, the actors interviewed and surveyed in the value chains may not have perceived these legal areas as relevant to their immediate needs or concerns. This situation could reflect a broader issue of limited awareness and access to information about intellectual property rights and their potential benefits for agricultural stakeholders. Addressing this knowledge gap is critical, as it might hinder the strategic use of legal tools that could otherwise enhance competitiveness and sustainability.

The findings also underscore the significant role of international and European Union (EU) legal frameworks in shaping agricultural trade dynamics, particularly for countries aiming to access the EU market. Compliance with stringent EU regulations, such as the General Food Law, sustainability standards, and environmental regulations, is a matter of legal obligation and a strategic necessity for maintaining and expanding market access. Case studies from Kenya, Uganda, and other countries highlight how aligning domestic laws with international agreements like the World Trade Organization's (WTO) Sanitary and Phytosanitary (SPS) Agreement can facilitate smoother trade flows and reduce barriers, thereby enhancing competitiveness.

However, the cost and complexity of compliance present significant challenges, especially for small-scale producers in developing countries. These producers often lack the necessary resources, knowledge, and institutional support to meet the EU's and other markets' rigorous standards. This gap indicates the critical need for capacity-building initiatives and institutional support to bridge this divide. Strengthening local institutions and providing targeted technical assistance can empower smallholder

farmers to comply with international standards and benefit from global trade opportunities, especially given the predominance of the EU's Directive on Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence (Directive 2024/1760) and EUDEFOR in current discussions on sustainable supply chains in Brussels.

Furthermore, aligning agricultural practices with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is a recurring theme in the case studies. Goals such as SDG 1 (No Poverty), SDG 2 (Zero Hunger), and SDG 13 (Climate Action) are consistently emphasized as essential for achieving both economic and environmental sustainability. For instance, case studies on the Ugandan coffee value chain and the South African wine industry show that integrating SDG-aligned practices can enhance sustainability and improve market access by meeting the growing demand for ethically sourced and sustainably produced goods in the EU market.

Another critical area of concern is the impact of legal and institutional frameworks on promoting social sustainability and equitable trade practices. Compliance with international labour standards, such as those set by the International Labour Organization (ILO), and adherence to human rights and due diligence are essential for ensuring fair labour practices in agricultural sectors. The case studies, particularly those focusing on bioethanol production in Brazil and sugarcane ethanol trade in Peru, reveal the gaps and challenges in enforcing these standards, underscoring the need for stronger regulatory mechanisms and more robust monitoring and reporting systems.

In conclusion, the findings of this report underscore the need for a multi-faceted approach to sustainable agricultural trade that integrates robust legal frameworks, capacity-building efforts, and targeted policy interventions. By addressing the gaps in legal coverage and enhancing the awareness and capacity of value chain actors, there is potential to foster more sustainable, equitable, and competitive agricultural trade practices that align with global development goals.